

TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

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Final design of Platforms and Networks solutions

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Description		
<i>3GPP</i>	3rd Generation Partnership Project	<i>eCPRI</i>	Evolved CPRI
<i>4G</i>	Fourth Generation of mobile communications	<i>EdgeApp</i>	Edge Application
<i>5G</i>	Fifth Generation of mobile communications	<i>EEC</i>	Edge Enabler Client
<i>5GC</i>	5G Core	<i>EES</i>	Edge Enabler Server
<i>5QI</i>	5G Quality of Service Identifier	<i>EIRP</i>	Equivalent Isotropic Radiated Power
<i>A5G</i>	Advanced 5G Technology	<i>EMCO</i>	Edge Multi-Cluster Orchestrator
<i>6G</i>	Sixth Generation of mobile communications	<i>eNB</i>	Evolved Node B
<i>AI</i>	Artificial Intelligence	<i>EPC</i>	Evolved Packet Core
<i>AIaaS</i>	AI as a Service	<i>ERC</i>	Ericsson España SA
<i>AIR</i>	Antenna Integrated Radio	<i>ETSI</i>	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
<i>API</i>	Application Programming Interface	<i>FEC</i>	Forward Error Correction
<i>APN</i>	Access Point Name	<i>FPS</i>	Frames Per Second
<i>AR</i>	Augmented Reality	<i>GAM</i>	Galleria d'Arte Moderna
<i>B5G</i>	Beyond 5G mobile network	<i>GDPR</i>	General Data Protection Regulation
<i>Bs5G</i>	Baseline 5G	<i>GSMA</i>	Global System for Mobile communications Association
<i>BBU</i>	Baseband Unit	<i>gNB</i>	gNodeB
<i>BE</i>	Best Effort	<i>GNSS</i>	Global Navigation Satellite System
<i>BIPT</i>	Belgisch Instituut voor postdiensten en telecommunicatie	<i>GPS</i>	Global Positioning System
<i>CAPIF</i>	Common API Framework	<i>GPU</i>	Graphics Processing Unit
<i>CAPEX</i>	Capital expenditure	<i>GUI</i>	Graphical User Interface
<i>CC</i>	Component Carrier	<i>HARQ</i>	Hybrid Automatic Repeat request
<i>CCTV</i>	Closed-Circuit TeleVision	<i>HTTPS</i>	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
<i>CGNAT</i>	Carrier-grade Network Address Translation	<i>HW</i>	Hardware
<i>CLAHE</i>	Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization	<i>IAM</i>	Identity Access Management
<i>CMU</i>	Compact Mobility Unit	<i>IEEE</i>	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
<i>CN</i>	Core Network	<i>IME</i>	Intent Management Entity
<i>CNC</i>	Computer Numerical Control	<i>IMEC</i>	Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre
<i>CNIT</i>	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni	<i>IP</i>	Internet Protocol
<i>COTS</i>	Commercial Off-the-Shelf	<i>IPSEC</i>	Internet Protocol Security
<i>CPE</i>	Customer-Premises Equipment	<i>IoT</i>	Internet of Things
<i>CPRI</i>	Common Public Radio Interface	<i>IRU</i>	Indoor Radio Unit
<i>CP</i>	Control Plane	<i>ISG</i>	Industry Specification Group
<i>CPU</i>	Central Processing Unit	<i>ITS</i>	Intelligent Transport Systems and Services
<i>CRC</i>	Cyclic Redundancy Check	<i>ITSS</i>	Infrastructure, Transportation and Security & Safety
<i>CTE</i>	Culture, Tourism, and Entertainment	<i>KPI</i>	Key Performance Indicator
<i>DBSCAN</i>	Depth-based spatial clustering of applications with noise	<i>KV</i>	Key Value
<i>DL</i>	Deep Learning	<i>KVI</i>	Key Value Indicator
<i>DQN</i>	Deep Q-network	<i>KVM</i>	Kernel-based Virtual Machine
<i>DRL</i>	Deep Reinforcement Learning	<i>LADN</i>	Local Area Data Network
<i>DSCP</i>	Differentiated Services Code Point	<i>LCM</i>	Life Cycle Manager
<i>DT</i>	Digital Twin	<i>LoS</i>	Line of Sight
<i>E2E</i>	End-to-end	<i>LPG</i>	Local Packet Gateway
<i>EAC</i>	Edge Application Client	<i>LTE</i>	Long Term Evolution
<i>EAS</i>	Edge Application Server	<i>MAC</i>	Medium Access Control
<i>eBPF</i>	extended Berkeley Package Filter	<i>MANO</i>	Management and Orchestration
		<i>MCI</i>	Mass Casualty Incident
		<i>MCS</i>	Modulation and Coding Scheme

<i>MEC</i>	Multi-Access Edge Computing	<i>RGB</i>	Red Green and Blue
<i>MIMO</i>	Multiple Input Multiple Output	<i>RIC</i>	RAN Intelligent Controller
<i>ML</i>	Machine Learning	<i>REST</i>	Representational State Transfer
<i>MNOs</i>	Mobile Network Operators	<i>RSA</i>	Rivest–Shamir–Adleman
<i>MnS</i>	Management Service	<i>RSU</i>	Roadside Unit
<i>MPTCP</i>	Multi-Path Transport Control Protocol	<i>RRU</i>	Radio Remote Unit
<i>MQTT</i>	MQ Telemetry Transport	<i>SA</i>	Standalone Architecture
<i>MT-M&O</i>	Multi-Technology Management and Orchestration	<i>SBA</i>	Service-Based Architecture
<i>NF</i>	Network Function	<i>SDN</i>	Software Defined Networking
<i>NFV</i>	Network Function Virtualization	<i>SDR</i>	Software Defined Radio
<i>NFVI</i>	Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure	<i>SEAL</i>	Service Enabler Architecture Layer
<i>NFVO</i>	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator	<i>SIM</i>	Subscriber Identity Module
<i>NPN</i>	Non-Public Network	<i>SNPN</i>	Stand-alone Non-Public Network
<i>NR</i>	New Radio	<i>SSH</i>	Secure Shell
<i>NR-DC</i>	NR-NR Dual Connectivity	<i>SVR</i>	Support Vector Regression
<i>NSA</i>	Non-Standalone Architecture	<i>TEI</i>	Ericsson Telecomunicazioni SpA
<i>NWDAF</i>	Network Data Analytics Function	<i>TDD</i>	Time-Division Duplex
<i>OAI</i>	Open Air Interface	<i>TIM</i>	Telecom Italia SPA
<i>OBU</i>	Onboard Unit	<i>TUIASI</i>	Technical University of IASI
<i>OC</i>	Open Call	<i>UAV</i>	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
<i>OPEX</i>	Operational expenditure	<i>UC</i>	Use Case
<i>ORO</i>	Orange Romania	<i>UE</i>	User Equipment
<i>OS</i>	Operating System	<i>UDM</i>	User Data Management
<i>OSM</i>	Open-Source MANO	<i>UP</i>	User Plane
<i>O-CU</i>	Open Centralized Unit	<i>UPF</i>	User Plane Function
<i>O-DU</i>	Open Distributed Unit	<i>URI</i>	Uniform Resource Identifier
<i>PAM</i>	Privileged Access Management	<i>URLLC</i>	Ultra-reliable low latency communication
<i>PCG</i>	Packet Core Gateway	<i>USB</i>	Universal Serial Bus
<i>PDF</i>	Probability Density Function	<i>TTI</i>	Transmission Time Interval
<i>PKI</i>	Public Key Infrastructure	<i>V2X</i>	Vehicle-to-Everything
<i>PNI-NPN</i>	Public Network Integrated Non Public Network	<i>VAL</i>	Vertical Application Layer
<i>PoliTO</i>	Politecnico di Torino	<i>VEC</i>	Vehicular Edge Computing
<i>PoC</i>	Proof of concept	<i>vEPC</i>	Virtual Evolved Packet Core
<i>PVGIS</i>	Photovoltaic Geographical Information System	<i>VIM</i>	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
<i>PRB</i>	Physical Resource Block	<i>vLAN</i>	Virtual Local Area Network
<i>PT</i>	Physical Twin	<i>VM</i>	Virtual Machine
<i>PV</i>	Photovoltaic	<i>VNF</i>	Virtual Network Function
<i>QoD</i>	Quality on Demand	<i>VPN</i>	Virtual Private Network
<i>QoS</i>	Quality of Service	<i>vRAN</i>	Virtualized RAN
<i>RAM</i>	Random Access Memory	<i>VR</i>	Virtual Reality
<i>RAN</i>	Radio Access Network	<i>VRU</i>	Vulnerable Road User
<i>RAT</i>	Radio Access Technology	<i>VXLAN</i>	Virtual Extensible Local Area Network
<i>RD</i>	Radio Dot	<i>WP</i>	World Package
<i>RDI</i>	Radio Dot Interface	<i>Wi-Fi</i>	Wireless Fidelity
<i>RE</i>	Renewable energy	<i>Xn</i>	The Interface between gNBs
		<i>XR</i>	Extended Reality
		<i>ZSM</i>	Zero-touch Service Management
		<i>ZTS</i>	Zero-Touch Service

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Executive Summary

TrialsNet focuses on deploying large-scale trials integrating a set of innovative Beyond 5G (B5G) technologies and applications. These applications spawn across different cutting-edge solutions, including robotics, metaverse, massive twinning and Internet of Sense in the context of the three different domains of (i) Infrastructure, Transportation, Safety and Security, (ii) eHealth & Emergency, and (iii) Culture, Tourism & Entertainment. Through its trials activities, and for each proposed use case (UC), TrialsNet is going to collect both quantitative and qualitative results of the users' experience which will be evaluated through proper methodologies and processes aiming at (i) elaborate on the potential limitations of the current network technologies in order to derive the requirements for the next mobile network generation and (ii) understand the level of acceptance of the proposed applications by the users also to reinforce the current B5G ecosystem.

In the above context, Work Package 2 (WP2) focuses on developing the platform and network solutions foundational to WP3, WP4, and WP5, which define and implement the use cases. The WP2 delivers the computing and network infrastructure, along with integration and security guidelines, ensuring secure and efficient trial execution while meeting the requirements of the other technical WPs. Requirements have been translated in first design of the platform and network solutions described in D2.1 "Preliminary design aspects for Platforms and Networks solutions" [1], then updated after the first cycle of development activities in D2.2 "Intermediate design of Platforms and Networks solutions" [2], integrating the feedbacks received from the technical WPs. The technologies deployed by WP2 are focused on network features that go beyond the Baseline 5G Technology (Bs5G) and provide a set of advanced functionalities, namely Advanced 5G Technology (A5G), as described in D2.1 [1].

Moreover, WP2 has established a strong synergy with WP6 from the very beginning of the project, initially to define relevant infrastructure and network KPIs, and subsequently to provide the technologies necessary for measuring the performance of the infrastructures during the trial activities. WP2 is also interacting with WP7, as Open Call projects uses or extends the currently available infrastructures, as described in Section 3.

The project's trials are being conducted in the four clusters located in Italy, Spain, Romania, and Greece. Regarding this aspect, it should be highlighted that even if the clusters have been conceived as independent infrastructures to provide a more flexible set of solutions to accommodate the specific requirements coming from the different use cases as well as the Open Call sub-projects, synergies between them are not precluded and have been created in the context of different activities. For example, UC6 "Mass Casualty Incident (MCI) and Emergency Rescue in Populated Area" is going to be integrated and experimented in two different infrastructures (i.e., the Greek cluster and the Madrid infrastructure within the Spanish cluster). Another example is the Horizontal innovation related to the Zero-touch Server Management (ZSM) that has been implemented in the Belgium experimental facility as well as the Iasi infrastructure.

The **Italian cluster** involves two trial sites, i.e., the Turin site and the Pisa site. The Turin site relies on the TIM 5G commercial network based on a 3GPP Rel-15 Non Standalone (NSA) deployment, with applications running on top of a virtualized infrastructure running at the CNIT premises. Service provisioning is managed by an innovative E2E orchestration solution provided by Nextworks, enabling the possibility to easily scale concurrent services in real-time during the (large scale) trials. The Pisa site instead spawns across the CNR campus in Pisa, the Fondazione Monasterio hospital [3] in Massa and the Ericsson's 5G laboratory in Genova, where a mmWave private network has been setup from scratch and where pre-trial tests were also conducted in the first phase of the project. Services and 5G network slices are orchestrated by the Ericsson Orchestrator, a system to manage and automate the lifecycle of applications and network resources, integrated with a distributed computing infrastructure from the Edge to the Cloud.

The **Spanish cluster** is located in Madrid, specifically within the 5Tonic [4] 5G laboratory. It relies on a 3GPP Rel-17 deployment, supporting A5G capabilities that provide the performances that are required to run the use cases. Once the pre-trial phase will be completed, a private network will be deployed at the WiZing Centre where the use cases will be trialled in a real-file environment during a basketball match. For this purpose, the network provided by Ericsson will consist in user plane (UP) and control plane (CP) installed in Leganes, where the actual applications run, while the Radio Access Network (RAN) at the WiZing Centre will be based on a 5G Standalone (SA) mmWave deployment, as the first full standalone 5G deployment over the 26GHz band in Europe. The proposed network solution is able to ensure high-speed as well as low-latency connectivity even in

demanding environments. The network's ability to handle heavy uplink traffic for multiple devices, including cameras, robots, and wearables, while optimizing coverage with sector-specific antenna placement, is a crucial feature for the real-time applications implemented by the use cases.

The **Romanian cluster** is composed by three different sites: in Iasi, two different deployments (outdoor 5G NSA and indoor 5G SA) are provided by Orange, utilizing their 5G commercial network. Pre-trial activities are conducted in Bucharest and in Antwerp (in Belgium), where the A5G technology of Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) framework developed by IMEC and Nextworks is tested before being implemented over the infrastructure in Iasi. The Romanian cluster integrates 5G SA and NSA hybrid network solutions, Edge Computing, and video analytics. The UC1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” and UC4 “Smart Traffic Management” benefit from a robust design based on both Bucharest and Iasi 5G Labs’ resources and an outdoor 5G coverage in the trials’ locations. A key innovation is the deployment of a 5G SA local UPF and Edge Computing servers at the Iasi 5G Lab datacenter, providing low-latency video analytics. This architecture also includes a dedicated URLLC slice ensuring prioritized latency of around 8 ms, crucial for real-time applications. The successful activation of 5G SA and NSA hybrid mode and initial field tests in the Iasi area confirm the system’s ability to handle real-time traffic, with high uplink and downlink performances.

The **Greek cluster** involves several locations in Athens, including public venues and the Athens International Airport facilities which are covered by a 5G commercial network. In addition, WINGS provides an experimental network infrastructure, integrating a private 3GPP Rel-15 NSA deployment with distributed cloud and Edge infrastructures with A5G capabilities, which are used to develop and test the use cases’ applications before the actual deployment during the trial phase.

This deliverable presents the results of the WP2 activities carried out since the previous document D2.1 [1]. In addition to the infrastructure design and implementation activities, this document outlines how the different hardware and software solutions have been integrated to build the actual infrastructures. Almost all the platform and network solutions in each cluster have reached the level of readiness to host the project’s trial activities as well as the Open Call projects. At time of writing this document, the Turin site, within the Italian cluster, has already hosted the trials of UC5 “Control Room in Metaverse” and UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse”.

A following section of this document is dedicated to the TrialsNet’s infrastructure extension through the Open Call. Thanks to the onboarding of 24 sub-projects, new use cases as well as new platform and network solutions have been integrated in the TrialsNet ecosystem, based on the categorization into Option 1 (i.e., new use cases or enhancements of existing ones implemented over the TrialsNet’s infrastructures) and Option 2 (i.e., new use cases implemented over new infrastructures) sub-projects. A description of the sub-projects’ infrastructures is provided.

The deliverable also reports on the security aspects that have been considered in the context of the infrastructures deployed by the project. For this reason, specific activities have been addressed to ensure that the platforms, networks solutions, and devices meet all the requirements in terms of security. In particular, security involves all the measures and strategies to protect information systems as well as the humans that interact with them during the trial phases. This document presents, in a dedicated section, how information systems, networks, and data have been protected from unauthorized access and from other types of threats. Among them, cloud and virtualization security outlines how services exposed through public endpoints are kept protected from external threats; Edge and far Edge security describes the protection of devices installed closer to the real users (like CPEs and IoT devices); network security ensures that the information that flows towards 5G devices meet all the integrity and confidentiality requirements; finally, trial security ensure that the actual users can safely interact with platform and devices.

A dedicated section is then dedicated to describe the updates on the activities on the TrialsNet innovations which, as in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2] have been categorized into Vertical and Horizontal innovations. Horizontal innovations are related to transversal B5G/6G functionalities such as ZSM. Vertical innovations instead are related to specific UCs, for example, automatic orchestration of network slice resources. The project has made advancements through both Horizontal and Vertical innovations. Key achievements include the development of a ZSM framework that enables cross-domain integration, automation, and real-time decision-making across various network infrastructures. Additionally, energy-aware applications for B5G/6G networks have been further developed. Vertical innovations include AI-driven solutions for diagnostics and resource efficiency,

particularly in infrastructure management and crowd monitoring. In this context, the project finalized the design of an automatic orchestration system for network slices, ensuring end-to-end QoS.

Finally, this deliverable presents updates on the sustainability solutions from the infrastructure perspective introduced by the project, focusing on self-sustainable energy harvesting, energy utilization, and energy-aware application design. It discusses the development of an energy sustainability model for self-sufficient systems, incorporating renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic panels and energy storage. The model evaluates performance metrics, sustainability targets, and cost constraints to ensure optimal system design. Additionally, the document explores the integration of energy-aware applications within the ZSM framework, aiming to optimize energy consumption in 5G and future 6G applications. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the sustainability solutions introduced by the project, initial KPIs have been identified based on the work performed in the context of WP6.

1 Introduction

In TrialsNet, the WP2 aims to support the trials execution through the design and deployment of innovative platform and network solutions including advanced functionalities, to meet the Use Case requirements. The large-scale trials performed by the project will help to identify eventual limitations of the current network technologies and, consequently, to define the baseline requirements for the next generation networks (such as the 6G). On the other side, through the involvement of real users and different types of verticals, the trials will also support the boosting of the future 5G deployments thanks to the innovative applications related to the use cases proposed by the project and implemented in the context of WP3, WP4, and WP5.

This document is organized in the following sections:

Section 2 describes for each trial site the updates on the development of the platform and network solutions with respect to the last WP2 deliverable D2.2 [2] highlighting the final design and the progress on the deployment activities. Key updates include the refinement of network capabilities, with advancements in Bs5G and A5G technologies, as well as the integration of new innovations to meet the specific requirements of the use cases.

Section 3 summarizes the relevant aspects related to the platform and network solutions that are going to be used by the Open Call sub-projects.

Section 4 describes the security mechanisms that have been implemented in each trial sites, covering the equipment and functionalities that build the overall infrastructures that includes user devices, radio access network, core network, as well as cloud and virtualization technologies to the Edge and far Edge.

Sections 5 and 6 present updates and outcomes of the innovation and sustainability activities carried out between the release of D2.2 [2] and the submission of this document.

Finally, Section 7 reports the conclusions, which summarize the key outcomes of the document, setting the baseline for the next WP2 activities.

2 Updates on TrialsNet clusters infrastructures activities

This section provides an overview on the TrialsNet’s platform and network solution latest development activities for each cluster (Italian, Spanish, Romanian and Greek). The Italian cluster includes two sites in Turin (Section 2.1) and Pisa (Section 2.2), while Spain, Romania, and Greece each have one site (Section 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, and 2.6). The Romanian cluster is utilizing an experimental infrastructure setup at IMEC, in Belgium, mainly for pre-trial testing activities. Even if conceived as independent infrastructures, the project’s clusters also created synergies in the context of different activities. For example, UC6 is going to be integrated and experimented in both the Greek and Spanish clusters. Additionally, Horizontal innovations like ZSM have been tested in both experimental facilities in Belgium and Iasi infrastructure, highlighting the collaborative nature of the project.

TrialsNet identified two reference technology sets for platform and network solution development as outlined in D2.1 [1]. The Bs5G represents the foundational capabilities available across all trial sites, serving as the starting point for use case development and as a benchmark for measuring initial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The A5G enhances network and service-level functionalities derived from planned improvements and feedback from initial use case deployments. This approach allows TrialsNet to refine its infrastructures and optimize their performances. Figure 1 recalls the mapping of these technologies across TrialsNet sites (where * means at service level only).

Figure 1. TrialsNet components and functionalities in different sites with reference to Bs5G and A5G.

2.1 Italian cluster (Turin site)

This section describes the status of platform and network solutions for the Turin site of the Italian cluster in which UC5 “Control Room in Metaverse”, UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse” and UC13 “Extended Reality (XR) Museum Experience” are implemented.

As already described in D2.2 [2], the Turin site in the Italian cluster includes a very extensive set of technologies, already developed in 5G EVE [5] and 5G-TOURS [6] projects, plus others software components (XR platform and the Symphony Internet of Things).

The platform includes a wide 5G coverage (based on TIM commercial network) with private Access Point Name (APN), an OpenStack cloud facility, and has been designed ready to host Open Call sub-projects where required.

2.1.1 Final design of platforms and networks solutions

The current status of the Turin site, in terms of infrastructure and components is up and running, thanks to the legacy of the previous projects. Figure 2 shows the final architecture of the site, including the Lab 5G Packet Core, supporting the Pisa Cluster via Virtual Private Network (VPN) connection.

Figure 2. Final architecture of Torino Cluster.

The infrastructure is maintained efficient by on-demand activities (mainly software maintenance) to guarantee the support of the UCs needs.

2.1.2 Progress on deployment activity

The deployment activities of the Turin site involved the integration of the latest development on the Symphony IoT Platform, which is the component, deployed as a Virtualized Network Function (VNF) within the Turin Site, that manages the lifecycle of sensor data in the Control Room and Metaverse use case, with data transmitted via the TIM 5G network. It connects to field sensors through a Hardware Abstraction Layer, using an “Message Queuing Telemetry Transport” (MQTT) driver to handle the data, and presents it via a Graphical User Interface (GUI) embedded in the Mozilla Hub [7] metaverse (as shown in Figure 3). The data is stored in the platform’s internal storage system (fvStorage), which includes a database and provides a REST API for external access.

Figure 3. Symphony Platform GUI embedded in the Metaverse Control Room tool.

During the period since the delivery of D2.2 [2] the Symphony Platform has been extended to support new API to expose the data gathered from the sensors. In details, two interfaces have been developed:

- A REST Based API for query-based requests.
- A Pub/Sub MQTT interface to connect to a stream of data.

An example of the REST based API to retrieve data gathered from the counting people sensor is:

```
POST /sensors/box
BODY
{
  "start": "<Timestamp Start>",
  "end": "<Timestamp End>",
  "limit": <Max Number of Samples>
}
```

The payload includes the following parameters:

- **"start"**: Start time for retrieving data, formatted in ISO 8601 as 2023-11-01T10:00:00Z.
- **"end"**: End time for the data range, formatted in ISO 8601 as 2023-11-30T10:00:00Z.
- **"limit"**: Maximum number of results to return (set to 10).

An example of the expected output is:

```
{
  "measurements": [
    {"timestamp": "2023-11-30T09:15:03Z", "counting": 3},
    {"timestamp": "2023-11-30T09:17:18Z", "counting": 2},
    .... ]
}
```

The expected output includes:

- **measurements**: An array of objects, each representing a measurement taken by the sensor within the specified date range. Each object in this array contains:
 - **timestamp**: A string formatted in ISO 8601 (e.g., "2023-11-30T09:15:03Z"), indicating the exact time when the measurement was recorded.
 - **counting**: An integer value representing the measurement count recorded by the sensor at that specific timestamp.

The Publish Subscribe MQTT interface to retrieve live data is reachable through the following parameters:

```
Host: trialsnet.polito.it
Port: 2883
Topic: sensors
```

An example of data sample is:

```
{
  "timestamp": "2024-01-12 10:47:14.901390",
  "counting": 7,
```

```

"bloom_filter": "<bloom_filter in binary code>"
}

```

where:

- **timestamp:** A string representing the date and time when the measurement was taken, formatted as "YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS.ssssss".
- **counting:** An integer value indicating the measurement count recorded by the sensor.
- **bloom_filter:** A placeholder indicating the presence of a bloom filter in binary code format, which is used for efficiently checking membership in a set.

Symphony, as most of the IoT platforms do, is able to process data from heterogeneous data sources. Thanks to the southbound interface, which is in charge of implementing the technologies to fetch data from different data sources, the platform embeds mechanisms to translate the information model of the incoming data to the internal one that is defined through the internal modules defining the system ontology. Once the data updates are processed by the system, the northbound (REST and MQTT) interfaces send updates to the external subscribers notifying that the new values for the sensors are available.

Symphony is currently connected to sensors installed in the Turin trial area (i.e. the “Parco del Valentino”), gathering information about the number of people in the area, collected by two Raspberry Pi [8] installed in two different poles.

2.1.3 Performed trials

The trial of UC5 “Control Room in Metaverse” was successfully held on 15 October 2024. This involved 18 agents from safety and security forces of the Turin municipality. The use case simulated a serious accident involving two injured people at the Parc of Valentino. The following devices were used:

- 4 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for the control room operators), connected via Wi-Fi to 2 CPE routers.
- 8 5G tablets (Samsung A9 and Lenovo M10 and P11), for the agents onsite to communicate and upload images/sounds/videos, connected directly to the 5G network.
- 2 5G smartphones (Samsung Galaxy), one for uploading images from the drone and the other to take KPI measurements onsite, connected directly to the 5G network.
- 1 Hikvision streaming video camera installed onsite, connected directly to the 5G network.
- 1 DJI drone with streaming camera (it was just manually held because of GDPR constraints), connected to the network via Wi-Fi and smartphone.
- A box with people counting sensors installed onsite, connected directed to the 5G network.
- 2 ZTE 5G CPE at the Talent Garden.

The Trial of UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse” was successfully held on 14 and 15 November at the Parco del Valentino and the nearby Talent Garden building in Turin. It involved 130 students and 6 professors from the secondary school Liceo Artistico Cottini in Turin and 15 staff from the TrialsNet partners. The following devices were used:

- 8 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for the VR combat phase) including 4 spares for recharge, connected via Wi-Fi to 2 CPE router.
- 10 5G tablets (Samsung A9 and Lenovo M10 and P11), for the groups involved in the game, connected directly to the network.
- 8 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for VR Prize phase) including 4 spares for recharge, connected via Wi-Fi to a CPE router.
- 3 5G ZTE CPE in the Telent Garden.
- Person counting sensor box in the Valentino Park.

Both trials were concluded successfully, meeting the expected KPIs and Key Value Indicators (KVI)s. On the KPIs side, the infrastructure of the Turin site (encompassing the commercial 5G network coverage and the platforms depicted in Figure 1) effectively supported the trials’ setup. Nevertheless, especially for UC5, it is likely that additional capacity will be required to handle larger incidents involving a higher number of equipment’s and portable devices. Concerning the KVI)s, according to the preliminary feedbacks received, the

proposed applications met the users' expectations. A detailed description of the performed trials of UC5 and UC12, the performed measurements for both KPIs and KVI, and related examination of the findings will be reported in the final deliverables D3.3 and D5.3 respectively. The overall results evaluation (including the results coming from the other project's trials) will be captured in D6.3.

2.2 Italian cluster (Pisa site)

The Pisa site of the Italian cluster, located in the CNR Campus, serves as the hub for the deployment and validation of three use cases: UC7 "Remote Proctoring," UC8 "Smart Ambulance," and UC9 "Hannes Prosthesis". The Pisa site will also host the sub-project "COMO5: Continuous Monitoring of patients with chronic disease via 5G" (named COMO5), which was selected through the Open Call process.

As detailed in D2.2 [2], other sites connected with the Pisa location play a crucial role in the deployment and validation of these use cases:

- The TIM site in Turin hosts the 5G Packet Core and 5G User Data Management (UDM).
- The "Ospedale del Cuore" hospital in Massa hosts the training surgical room for UC7 and the emergency unit for UC8.
- The Ericsson 5G laboratory in Genoa initially hosts the UC9 systems before they are moved to the Pisa site.

2.2.1 Final design of platforms and networks solutions

The main components of the platforms and network solutions were already described in Section 2.2.2 of D2.2 [2]. Figure 4 provides an updated version of the trial architecture, with respect to Figure 11 of D2.2 [2]. In particular, compared to what was reported in D2.2 [2], the present figure provides greater detail regarding the devices used in the various use cases, adds the use case related to the COMO5 sub-project, and adds the blocks related to disturbance traffic indoor (DI) and outdoor (DO). The disturbance traffic is used to create a high traffic load condition on the mobile network to demonstrate that the critical services associated with the use cases continue to operate with the expected performance even under these particular "wors case" traffic conditions. It was also specified that the connection between the Pisa site and the Massa hospital is made via an optical fiber.

Figure 4. High level architecture for the Pisa site (updated October 2024).

TIM Core network and 5G UDM is based on Ericsson's dual-mode solution for 5G EPC and 5GC Network Functions (NFs) consist entirely of microservice-based cloud native NFs that deliver 5GC and 5G Evolved Packet Core (EPC) functionalities, including support for new Service-Based Architectures (SBA).

The dual-mode 5G Core solution enables new network capabilities that allow to release the full potential of new 5G-enabled use cases and secures a smooth migration from existing 2G/3G/4G network capabilities. This solution combines 3GPP EPC and 5GC network architectures into a common cloud native software platform.

The diagram in Figure 5 highlights the separation of control plane functions (located in Turin) from the user plane functions (located in Pisa). This distribution allows for flexible deployment and management of network resources. This image is an architectural diagram of the 5GC network deployment.

Figure 5. TIM 5G Network (Turin and Pisa).

Here's a breakdown of the components:

Data Layer (Turin):

- Cloud Core Data-Storage Manager (v. 1.7 CP1) [9] including the UDR (Unified Data Repository), responsible for storing subscription data and policy-related information, acting as a centralized database for various network functions.

Control Plane (Turin):

- Cloud Core Resource Controller (v 1.7.11-2) [10], including:
 - NSSF (Network Slice Selection Function): Manages network slicing, helping to allocate resources based on different service requirements.
 - NRF (Network Repository Function): Maintains an updated repository of available network functions and their profiles, facilitating network function discovery.
- Cloud Core Subscription Manager (v. 1.8.3) [11], including:
 - UDM (Unified Data Management): Manages user subscription profiles and authentication credentials.
 - AUSF (Authentication Server Function): Handles authentication for user devices connecting to the network.
- Packet Core Controller (v.1.21) [5] delivering access control, session control, mobility, and gateway control functions, including:

- AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function): Manages device registration, connection, and mobility.
- SMF (Session Management Function): Oversees session management and allocation of IP addresses.

User Plane (Pisa):

- Packet Core Gateway (PCG): (v 1.22), hosted in a Local Packet Gateway (LPG) (v. 1.3), delivering the user plane (UPF). LPG provides a single server bare metal cloud native solution to host the PCG. LPG is located at inside Pisa Site premises close to the network edge for optimum performance. UPF handles data forwarding and routing for user traffic, serving as the gateway for the user plane.

2.2.2 Progress on deployment activity

In March 2024, the contractor responsible for the hardware installation at the Pisa site was selected, and discussions commenced with this company to outline the timeline for the hardware installation at the CNR Campus building. The installation work began in May, and the network has been operational since July. Specifically, both the radio antennas and the baseband equipment, supplied by Ericsson and described in D2.2 [2] Section 2.2.2, has been part of the installation. Via VPN, the baseband system has been remotely connected to the core network hosted in Turin as illustrated in Figure 6.

At the time of release of the current deliverable, the 5G network has been completely deployed based on the 3GPP SA Rel-16 [12] architecture and it is operating over a bandwidth of 200 MHz in the 26 GHz mmWave spectrum (i.e., 26.9-27.1 GHz). Figure 6 illustrates the locations of the main network components (antennas, radio and cloud systems in the server room) in relation to the CNR Campus.

Figure 6. Deployed 5G network systems and their location in the area.

Before installing and activating the antennas, a specific coverage study related to emissions has been done (in cooperation with the company Selekra Italia) and a report has been produced in June 2024 reporting both the indoor and outdoor radiation diagrams. The planned emission values, on which the power of the antennas should be adjusted, have been identified to comply with the constraint of not exceeding 6 V/m, calculated at a height of 1.50 m, according to the regulations of "Legge quadro n° 36 del 2001" and the "Decreto Legislativo 179 del 18/10/2012", in relation to precautionary measures and quality objectives.

More specifically, an Ericsson AIR 1281 [13] antenna has been installed at the indoor CNR site designated for the UC7, UC8, and UC9 and COMO5 test activities, while a second Ericsson AIR 1281 antenna has been installed outdoors, facing the parking area where the UC8 experiments are scheduled. These antennas will also be used to transmit what is referred to as "disturbance traffic" for both indoor (DI) and outdoor (DO). The purpose of this traffic is to generate a significant load on the 5G network to demonstrate effective traffic prioritization. This ensures that critical medical data is transmitted reliably, even under conditions of network congestion. iPerf

[14] tool is used to generate disturbance traffic by creating high-bandwidth data streams that can be injected in the network and captured by the CPEs according to the scheme of Figure 4. Running multiple instances of iPerf can simulate higher levels of network congestion.

In parallel, a rack has been installed in the CNR server room (not far from the mentioned indoor room) to host the baseband system Ericsson Baseband Unit BB6651 [15] which supports the selected mmWave bands. The two antennas are in the same building where the server room is located to minimize the need for cabling. In addition, the rack also contains systems that allow VPN connection with the TIM site in Turin and fiber optic connection with the hospital in Massa.

Performance testing at the user equipment level will be conducted as soon as the CPE will be activated and connected to the terminals and devices.

2.3 Spanish cluster

Following sub-sections describe the progress of the laboratory infrastructure located in Madrid to perform UC1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring”, UC6 “Mass Casualty Incident” and UC10 “Immersive Fan Engagement” use cases. The network solution evolved from a 5G SA NR-Dual Connectivity (5G SA midband plus 5G SA high band) to a 5G SA FR2 (5G SA high band only). The new configuration required a software (SW) upgrade of the gNB and new hardware (HW), i.e., CPEs 5G FR2 SA and more than 1 antenna sector, considering the areas to be covered in the WiZink Center.

2.3.1 Final design of platforms and networks solutions

As explained in the deliverable D2.2 [2], an upgrade of the infrastructure from existing NR Midband configuration to Rel-17 NR SA mmWave-based was necessary, so the design of a mmWave-based system has been completed. This includes the Low-Level Design for the system and interconnection equipment within the flight rack, that is, the mmWave antennas, LPG [16], Router 6675 [17] and Baseband 6648 [18], together with the existing 5G Core infrastructure already existing in 5Tonic Lab [4].

On July 22nd 2024, the TrialsNet team from UC1, UC6, and UC10 visited the WiZink Center in Madrid [19] which is the biggest indoor arena in Madrid with a capacity up to 17000 spectators [20]. During this visit, decisions were taken regarding location of antennas, CPEs and devices for all the use cases.

Figure 7. Close Details of Basketball Court inside WiZink Center.

Although from network design perspective the solutions to be used in UC1, UC6, and UC10, that is the use of mmWave-only 5G SA Network, were ready and defined in the past, the final design of the solution to be used on these use cases has been completed, as it can be seen in the next high level design in Figure 8.

Figure 8. High Level Network Solution Design for UC1, UC6, and UC10 experimentation area.

The network will provide the coverage with 3 sectors, each one using a mmWave AIR 5322 radio [21]:

Sector 1 (S1)

This sector will cover the larger area (basketball court) providing mostly the uplink service to the cameras of UC10. Three mmWave Rel-17 CPEs will be connected to it, each one providing connectivity to a different camera. Figure 9 and Figure 10 depict the setup for the Sector 1.

Figure 9. Sector 1 view, with Cameras and CPE locations.

Figure 10. Sector 1 view, with AIR location.

Sector 2 (S2)

This sector will provide NR Coverage to the UC10 Production Set and to the Wi-Fi access point that will provide the in-venue experience to the smartphones. These smartphones will not be directly connected to the mmWave 5G SA network since there are no commercial smartphones available in the market yet. Figure 11 depicts the Sector 2 setup.

Figure 11. Sector 2 view, with AIR and CPE locations.

Sector 3 (S3)

This sector, located in C/Goya access, will provide connectivity to UC1 and UC6, reusing 2 CPEs from the Sector 1, given that the events will not collide in time. The devices to be connected to this sector vary from robots, cameras, lidars that will provide data flows to the servers in the control room, all within the same sector. Therefore, the traffic is expected to be exactly symmetrical in terms of downlink and uplink since the devices will do mostly uplink traffic while the servers and control room will do mostly downlink traffic. The UC1 and UC6 devices that require certain mobility in the area (i.e., robots and wearables) will be connected through a Wi-Fi access point connected to the 5G NR mmWave CPE since there are no portable 5G CPEs in the market that support 5G SA mmWave-only networks at the time of the implementation. Figure 12 depicts the setup of Sector 3.

Figure 12. UC1 and UC6 location, including CPEs and AIR.

The total number of CPEs needed will be 4, with UC10 will use all simultaneously, while UC6 and UC1 will reuse two units. In general, in order to the devices to interact and connect with each other, fixed IP is needed when provisioning the SIM cards, so that the CPE have always the same IP address and port forwarding can be configured accordingly. Thanks to this, the control center can reach the desired devices through the public IP with the configured ports. Then the traffic is forwarded to the configured local LAN address of the CPE where the devices are connected.

2.3.2 Progress on deployment activity

To support the remote tests on the premises, a flight rack with mmWave antennas and UPF on the Edge is used. This will require the new antennas AIR5322 for mmWave, a Router 6675 and a new Baseband 6648. The assembly of all the flight Rack components, in an equipment called “Penguin” has been done in Spring 2024 in 5Tonic Lab as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Assembly of the Penguin flight rack components in 5Tonic Lab.

Once the assembly and interconnection were completed, the rest of the equipment, including Baseband, Radio, local Router and Local UPF, was integrated with the latest available software at the time and tested. Since the 5G mmWave-only CPE devices were not ready to test yet, the RAN system was initially using the existing 5G SA mid-band coverage in the lab as anchor layer and using the mmWave carriers as secondary cells in an NR-DC configuration. The Xn interfaces were created between the new mmWave-only gNodeB and the existing mid-band gNodeB. A SW upgrade was completed 2 months later to the latest SW Release available (NR24.Q2) to support 3x800Mhz mmWave cells without uplink speed limitations, given that the design and use of the system expects heavy uplink traffic.

Four prototype CPEs based on Qualcomm’s SDX75 chipset have been leased for the project. Several preparations work, involving SW flashing and firmware updates, band filtering, configuring PS-only Data-Centric mode, and local ports configuration, were done before they were able to attach to the network. The Connectivity mode was initially set to NR-DC, that is, using existing 5G SA midband coverage as anchor and the new mmWave coverage as traffic layer, since it was the first time these kinds of prototype devices were used in Europe and more specifically in 5Tonic Lab. This solution is typically used in commercial mmW networks and has been used in the past in 5Tonic Lab, therefore the introduction of the prototype CPEs is done first with an already validated and tested network solution.

Figure 14. Four mmWave CPE Prototypes (l), mmWave AIR 5322 (m), and Penguin Flight Right (r).

Initial tests were done in NR-DC mode to confirm that there were no end-to-end issues in neither the 5G Core Network, Radio Network and CPE device, reaching values very close to the theoretical values as it can be observed in Figure 15. The 8CCs (Component Carriers) are used in the downlink and 4CC are used in the uplink, per sector. Each CC has 100Mhz Bandwidth, so total used Bandwidth is 800Mhz in downlink and 400Mhz in uplink. Though the system is integrated and ready for 3 sectors, only 1 sector is configured to avoid inter-sector interference given the size of the lab rom.

Figure 15. Peak throughput obtained October 4th, 2024, using NR-DC configuration and TCP traffic.

Once NR-DC configuration and performance was secured, both CPE and Penguin were configured in FWA mode or mmWave-only mode. From network and gNodeB perspective, the Xn interfaces to the mid-band gNodeB were deleted and the software feature “NR Standalone High-Band for Fixed Wireless Access” was

activated with the corresponding configuration parameters. This feature allows the mmWave UEs to attach directly to the NR Primary Cells, perform the Random-Access procedure and get in RRC_CONNECTED state. The NR mmWave-cells now transmits the SIB1 in the downlink, so that the UE can detect the cell directly and initiate the Random-Access Procedure. From prototype CPE perspective, specific configuration files are set up in the device and NR-DC Mode is disabled. The four Qualcomm Prototype CPEs and the SIM cards are provisioned with a fixed-IP configuration as requested by the design. The Ethernet interface of the CPE is activated and configured. The CPE will act as an 5G access point for the devices, using the LAN for all the devices. Finally, routing is configured, since fixed DHCP Lease is needed as well as port forwarding.

On October 21st the first 5G SA session was completed, using mmWave-only configuration. The CPE was able to attach to the network and perform traffic successfully, as can be observed in Figure 16 and in Figure 17.

Figure 16. Snapshot of the successful RRC Setup trace in mmWave-only cell.

Figure 17. Snapshot of the gNodeB console where 1 UE attached to the FR2-cells can be observed.

Similar performance is obtained as in NR-DC configuration, as it can be observed in Figure 18, noting that no optimization is performed yet to maximize performance, in terms of CPE orientation or network configuration. 1 Sector is used for the measurements, with 8CC in downlink and 4 CC in uplink, therefore with a total bandwidth of 800Mhz in downlink and 400Mhz in uplink.

Figure 18. Peak throughput obtained October 18th, 2024, using FWA mmWave-only configuration.

Pings to www.google.com (8.8.8.8) are measured, showing an outstanding round-trip delay (Figure 19), considering that part of this traffic is outside, and therefore out of control, of the 5Tonic Lab. Typical values of a similar system using mid-band coverage instead are around 15ms, so the mmWave-only system improves significantly the latency.

```
~# ping 8.8.8.8
PING 8.8.8.8 (8.8.8.8): 56 data bytes
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=0 ttl=111 time=3.920 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=1 ttl=111 time=6.344 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=2 ttl=111 time=6.140 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=3 ttl=111 time=5.935 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=4 ttl=111 time=4.794 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=5 ttl=111 time=5.721 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=6 ttl=111 time=6.354 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=7 ttl=111 time=6.275 ms
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: seq=8 ttl=111 time=5.259 ms
^C
--- 8.8.8.8 ping statistics ---
9 packets transmitted, 9 packets received, 0% packet loss
round-trip min/avg/max = 3.920/5.638/6.354 ms
```

Figure 19. Round-trip delay measured using pings to google.com using FWA mmWave-only configuration.

Following the activities described above, the network solution can be considered ready for the trial phase.

2.4 Romanian cluster

The Romanian cluster hosts the deployment and validation of the UC1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” and UC4 “Smart Traffic Management” and is based in Iasi, leveraging both the indoor 5G SA infrastructure from the Bucharest and Iasi Orange 5G Labs as well as the outdoor hybrid 5G NSA/SA commercial/private network provided by Orange Romania.

2.4.1 Final design of platforms and networks solutions

The final design of the 5G and Edge-Compute architecture for UC1 and UC4 was finalized and is indicated in Figure 20 and described in D2.2 [2]. The architecture will be implemented starting from the end of 2024, following the developments described in the next section, and will be based on the current on-field deployed hardware described in the following section. In this approach, the RAN equipment that covers the “Stefan cel Mare” pedestrian area is configured to support 5G SA & NSA hybrid mode. This enables the interconnection with ORO's Bucharest 5G Lab 5G SA Nokia Compact Mobility Unit (CMU) Core Network, facilitating control-plane traffic and access to available compute resources. The Iasi 5G Lab datacenter is the central point of this updated architecture. It hosts the 5G SA local UPF unit and the Edge Computing servers for video analytics applications of UC1 and UC4. The user-plane traffic coming from the Iasi 5G SA RAN units will be routed to the local UPF. Instead, the video surveillance feeds will be transmitted directly to the Iasi 5G Lab datacenter Edge servers. To do so, a dedicated Ultra-reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) slice will allow for a prioritized latency of about 8 ms E2E.

Furthermore, the final design of the Romanian testbed architecture also includes the integration of the VITAL-5G [22] production-ready Network Applications orchestration platform within the Bucharest and Iasi 5G Labs Edge-Cloud facilities. This deployment will allow TUIASI partners and 3rd parties, like the ones coming from the TrialsNet open call, to deploy their applications in a more efficient manner, streamlining the process of obtaining access to the needed virtual appliances (Kubernetes pods). This integration not only showcases the exploitation sustainability of technical solutions developed within research and innovation projects, but also highlights the importance of using user-friendly platforms allowing users outside of the telco space to interact with the network and Edge Computing resources in a programmatic approach.

Figure 20. Romanian testbed 5G and Edge Compute final architecture.

2.4.2 Progress on deployment activity

Regarding the deployment activities, one of the major developments was towards finalizing the Iasi 5G Lab associated datacenter. As showcased in Figure 21, the datacenter is ready, hosting four racks for servers and networking equipment. The datacenter is hosting the Iasi testbed 5G remote UPF and Edge Computing servers, that were recently interconnected with the central Core Network and IPFABRIC [23] (using the VXLAN protocol) networking equipment from the Bucharest 5G Lab, as depicted in Figure 22.

Figure 21. Iasi 5G Lab datacenter.

Figure 22. 5G remote UPF and Edge Computing servers deployed in the datacenter.

Supplementary, 5G SA+NSA hybrid mode was activated on the UC1 area radio site, and the first tests were run in-field, using a COTS UE (Motorola Edge 50 Pro – Qualcomm X63 5G modem), to validate the performance of this deployment in a real-world outdoor scenario. The tests were conducted in a day with busy pedestrian traffic in the UC1 area, showcasing the advantages of the private hybrid SA deployment in a congested commercial 5G NSA environment. As presented in Figure 23, the uplink throughput is reaching 60Mbps, the Down-link throughput is reaching 500Mbps and the average latency to the Internet is around 30ms.

Figure 23. 5G SA first validation tests within the UC1 area.

2.5 Romanian cluster (experimental facilities in Belgium)

As reported in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2], the experimental facilities in Belgium comprise several testbeds as small-scale experimental sites located in Antwerp and Ghent (Belgium), which are used as a complementary setup to the trial site in the Romanian cluster. This setup is used for performing pre-trial research and development activities, which are then transferred to the Romanian trial site. This section briefly reports the updates on the deployment activities related to Horizontal innovations on Zero-Touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) (Section 5.1.1) and Energy-aware application design for the Smart Highway testbed, as well as planned upgrades on the 5GOpen (Next-Gen) testbed [24] to be performed by the sub-projects “Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving” (named ATOS Driving) and “6GVision: Improvement of the 5GOpen testbed at imec with vision-aided mmW gNB” (named 6GVision).

The Smart Highway testbed is being actively used for wireless networking research in IMEC, focusing on the automotive context. It offers Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication capabilities, as well as distributed and Edge Computing nodes that can be used for hosting and maintaining services and data processing units. As reported in D2.2 [2], the computing-communication continuum consists seven Roadside Units (RSUs) and two Onboard Units (OBUs) deployed on the test vehicle(s), which are utilized as far and extreme Edge Computing units, respectively. This experimental facility is heavily used for testing and validation of the advanced network technologies designed in the TrialsNet project, such as ZSM (A5G capability), which have been stepwise transferred to Iasi trial site (with first integration steps with LCM component in the Nextworks platform), for the purpose of trialing UC4. Concerning 5G connectivity, the experimental/test 5G license for the frequency range 4035-4085 MHz (N77 band) has been granted to IMEC by regulatory body in Belgium.

The above-mentioned license has been extended to mmWave band: a 400MHz chunk of spectrum (from 26.5 - > 26.9GHz) and a maximum Equivalent Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP) of 14.25W, to support the execution of the sub-project 6GVision. This license is used for the 5GOpen testbed (or Next-Gen testbed), which offers indoor 5G Standalone (SA) connectivity, compliant with the OpenRAN design. As reported in D2.2 [2], this testing setup consists of multiple gNodeBs that are deployed indoors based on OpenAir Interface (OAI) with Free5G [25] and Open5GS [26] deployment for the 5G Core. The subset of these testbed components is also installed on one instance of one RSU located at the University Campus, offering 5G SA capabilities outdoors in the granted frequency range.

Figure 24. Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the ZSM framework deployed on the Smart Highway testbed.

2.5.1 Final design of platforms and networks solutions

The design of the Smart Highway remained the same compared to the D2.2 [2] deliverable, and as such, it has been used to perform further deployment and integration activities related to ZSM, which are reported in Section 5.1.1. In addition to that, the ZSM solution deployed on the Smart Highway testbed has been further extended to support the execution of the Open Call sub-project ATOS Driving. In this sub-project, 5G Core deployed on the TNO infrastructure in the Netherlands exposes several Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), with the goal to support Quality on Demand (QoD) features (requesting increased service quality from a 3rd party service) and dynamic metric retrieval from the TNO 5G testbed (Section 3.2). The TrialsNet ZSM solution has been extended to utilize these APIs to collect metrics from this specific testbed (multi-domain deployment of ZSM explained in Section 5.1.1), and to trigger QoD API based on the decisions made by the ZSM orchestrator (e.g., more network resources are needed for a specific service running in the TNO 5G infrastructure). The interaction between the ZSM orchestrator (running on the Smart Highway) and TNO 5G Core (5G network infrastructure in the Netherlands) is performed in two ways:

- **Dynamic metric retrieval:** ZSM orchestrator collects network performance metrics exposed on the Performance Metrics API. These metrics are analyzed by the orchestrator, compared against the requirements for the autonomous and teleoperated driving (use case of ATOS Driving), and used for making a final decision (scale up network resources, change QoS profile from low/medium to high, etc.).
- **Requesting Quality on Demand:** Once the decision is made, the ZSM orchestrator utilizes the QoD API to change the QoS profile of the designated service that is being actively utilized by the teleoperated/automated vehicle. The association of the request is made with the user device, i.e., the SIM card used in the 5G modem deployed in the vehicle.

The initial integration of ZSM with ATOS Driving has been finalized, whereas the tests and trials are planned for the upcoming period. Thus, the detailed report on performed activities with this sub-project will be provided in the final deliverable, i.e., D2.4.

Concerning the 5GOpen (Next-Gen) testbed, the upgrades planned by the sub-project 6GVision are in more detailed presented in Section 3.1.5.

2.5.2 Progress on deployment activity

The deployment activity for ZSM is planned in three phases:

- **Phase 1:** Design, development, and testing performed on the Smart Highway testbed. This phase also included a definition of a set of testing scenarios.
- **Phase 2:** Integration with the LCM module running on the Nextworks platform in Italy. This intermediate step was important for ensuring smooth communication between ZSM orchestrator (decision-making logic) and LCM module (maintaining Kubernetes cluster where services are running and managing those services by implementing the decisions propagated by the ZSM orchestrator).
- **Phase 3:** Deployment and testing performed on the Iasi infrastructure. This phase includes the deployment of both ZSM and LCM modules in the designated virtual machines running on the 5G Edge platform of ORO network deployed in Iasi.

All these activities are in detail presented in Section 5.1.1, but here some of the relevant results are showcased to reflect on the way how ZSM operates on any trial site location. For instance, Figure 25 shows the GUI of the ZSM framework deployed on the Smart Highway testbed, which includes the small-scale view on the location of RSUs, as well as the measurements on end-to-end latency (measured at the client/vehicle side and reported to ZSM on the network edge), CPU load, and power consumption on each of the RSUs.

A more detailed view on the results is shown in Figure 25, which also shows the selected node for the deployment, i.e., RSU2. This particular deployment is selected by the ZSM orchestrator due to the lowest end-to-end latency and the power consumption on that Edge Computing node. It is important to note that the end-to-end latency is a prioritized metric due to the nature of UC4 application, which requires ultra-low latency and high reliability given that it involves the interaction with the Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs). Nevertheless, if the end-to-end latency between the user (vehicle) and two Edge Computing nodes/deployments is not significantly different, then power consumption is prioritized and the node with lower consumption is selected. This is just

to prove the concept and feasibility of taking into account power consumption measurements, but a more sophisticated logic can be implemented to make the overall use of the Edge Computing infrastructure in 5G SA ecosystem sustainable in a long haul.

Figure 25. Measurements collected by the ZSM orchestrator on the Smart Highway testbed.

The results shown in Figure 26 and Figure 27 refer to the deployment obtained in the Phase 2, and they show how the ZSM changes the decision about the selected node for service deployment from K8s-Cluster-4 to K8s-Cluster-2 due to the changes in the end-to-end latency. It is important to note the values of the end-to-end latency are significantly higher in this case, as the traffic between the server application deployed in the K8s cluster running in Italy on the Nextworks platform and the client application running in the test vehicle on the Smart Highway in Belgium is routed over the public internet. The actual values of the end-to-end latency are expected to be minimal when the tests are performed in Iasi 5G SA infrastructure, where the trials will be performed.

Figure 26. Measurements collected by the ZSM orchestrator with the Kubernetes cluster on the NXW platform.

Running Nodes: 4 | Selected Node: K8s-Cluster-2

Auto select node

Track selected node

Node	CPU (%)	Memory (%)	Storage (Gb)	Latency (Ms)
k8s-cluster-1	0	1849614336		94.628
k8s-cluster-2	1.7	3191791616		85.903
k8s-cluster-3	1.15	1581174784		88.988
k8s-cluster-4	0	1849618432		93.089

Figure 27. Change in the decision on the service deployment based on the updated measurements.

2.6 Greek cluster

This section provides the progress of the Greek cluster where the lab tests (before actual field trials) of UC2 “Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management”, UC3 “Autonomous APRON”, UC6 “Mass Casualty Incident (MCI) and Emergency Rescue in Populated Area”, UC11 “Service Robots for Enhanced Passenger’s Experience”, and UC13 “Extended Reality (XR) Museum Experience” are taking place. In the next sub-sections, there is the progress on the design of platforms and networks solutions and the progress on deployment activity.

2.6.1 Final design of platforms and networks solutions

Figure 28 shows the final WINGS private testbed architecture according to D2.2 [2]. During the recent period, specific pre-trial tests have been conducted with the aforementioned infrastructure for evaluating the performance before the trial execution. Downlink/uplink throughput, round-trip and one-way latency have been assessed for UC2, UC3, UC6 and UC11 in the WINGS Campus network.

Figure 28. Final WINGS private testbed architecture.

In addition, the integration of AI provides advanced AI capabilities to the Greek site use cases, enabling them to leverage AI solutions and models to enhance their operations and applicability. Such algorithms include AI for image recognition as well as efficient resource management and diagnostics. The WINGS Campus provides E2E 5G/B5G functionality, along with extensive cloud and Edge Computing capabilities, leveraging the 3GPP Release-15 [26] as baseline.

The developed private 5G infrastructure offers significant advantages for enhancing connectivity, security, and control over the private network. One of the primary benefits is increased network reliability and performance.

Unlike public 5G networks, private 5G allows WINGS to design and tailor its networks to meet specific needs, such as optimizing bandwidth, latency, and coverage. This is especially critical in industries like transport and healthcare, where high-speed, low-latency communication is essential for communication of devices, and real-time A.I. functionality (e.g., object detection, crowd estimation etc.). By having dedicated resources, it can be ensured a more consistent and secure network performance, avoiding congestion and interference typical of public networks.

Another key benefit of private 5G infrastructure is enhanced security and data privacy. The installed private network enables WINGS to maintain control over the data, ensuring that sensitive information stays within the company’s infrastructure without relying on externals. As a result, WINGS created a robust and secure environment to support critical application and increase efficiency.

2.6.2 Progress on deployment activity

The deployment activity in the WINGS private testbed is finalized and presented in D2.2 [2]. Table 1 provides information on the WINGS private 5G network radio configuration in terms of radio access technology, cell power, frequency band, bandwidth, etc.

Table 1. WINGS private 5G network radio configuration.

Radio configuration	
Radio access technology	5G NR NSA
Network type	Experimental
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Non Standalone
Cell Power	1W
Frequency band	5G 3500 MHz
Bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 KHz
MIMO	Up to 4X4
Duplex mode	TDD

Considering the aforementioned equipment and the radio characteristics Figure 29 provides a test measurement of end-to-end latency (from mobile device to iperf server) which is measured in the WINGS 5G private network with an average value of 24ms.

Figure 29. Measurement of end-to-end latency in the WINGS 5G private network.

3 TrialsNet infrastructures extension through the Open Call

This section describes the TrialsNet platform and network solutions related to the implementation of the sub-projects introduced via the Open Call. These include new use cases (or improvement) implemented over the existing project's sites as well as new use cases on additional trial infrastructures complementing the ones of TrialsNet. The sub-projects have been categorized into three options defined in the Open Call launch:

- **Options 1a:** New use case(s) and field trials supported by one or more TrialsNet infrastructures in terms of platforms and network solutions,
- **Option 1b:** improvement of its use case(s) by the integration of software applications, features, devices, new users, and datasets,
- **Option 2:** New use case(s) leveraging on new additional field trial infrastructures such as experimental, private, and/or commercial network deployments.

This section highlights how each of the related infrastructures integrate diverse technological solutions to implement the different additional use cases. Figure 30 depicts the geographical distribution of the use cases coming from the sub-projects.

Figure 30. Distribution of the use cases coming from the sub-projects.

3.1 Options 1a and 1b sub-projects

3.1.1 Italian cluster (Turin site)

Between the several Open Call sub-projects that will perform their trials in Turin, sub-project DREAMPARK (sub-project ID #019) is categorized as an Option 1b since it will integrate with the current UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse” developed by TrialsNet. Thus, the requirements of this solution have been analyzed in conjunction with the ones of UC12. This sub project will make use of the available 5G commercial network in the metropolitan area of Turin to reach their respective self-provided cloud hosts. For this reason, no extension to the TrialsNet infrastructure in Turin is planned.

3.1.2 Italian cluster (Pisa site)

The admitted Open Call sub-project hosted in Pisa, named COMO5 (sub-project ID #027), is an Option 1a. Such sub-project, as declared, will be deployed on the same infrastructure set up for the UC 7, UC8, and UC9 and does not require additional extension and specific configuration. The availability of all necessary systems for the trial implementation, specifically the two indoor and outdoor 5G antenna systems and the orchestrator, will expedite the execution phase. The execution will require the availability of both indoor and outdoor locations, however, these will not be required to be available at the same time, as different outdoor and indoor trials will be planned separately.

3.1.3 Spanish cluster

The two proposals leveraging the Spanish cluster are an Option 1a:

- Sub-project “Remote Coordination and Interworking of first responders in Emergency Situations” (sub-project ID #013): the proposal uses a HandHeld smartphone i-Safe Mobile IS540.2 [27], who has mid-band n77/n78 NR SA capability and no FR2 / mmWave capability. The area where these devices will be tested during the trials is the outdoor court in 5Tonic as shown in Figure 31;
- Sub-project “Skylink Vision” (sub-project ID #030): the 5G Modem to be used is a MicroHard Bullet 5G [28], that similarly to the other proposal, supports midband n77/n78 NR SA bands. Also this sub-project will run its trail in the basketball court in 5Tonic.

Figure 31. 5Tonic experimentation area.

Therefore, since both cases require NR mid-band coverage, and tests will be carried out in the basketball court, that already has NR mid-band coverage from the existing outdoor 5G mid-band radio, the infrastructure from the 5G Network perspective can be considered ready. Reservation and provisioning of the SIM cards for the tests have been done as well.

3.1.4 Romanian cluster

Based on the Open Call submitted proposals, three sub-projects have been selected for the Romanian cluster (i.e., two Option 1a and one Option 1b) and for which ORO provided the following support:

- Sub-project “AI/ML-based Preventive and Reactive Emergency handling” (named AI-PREMSET-MCX, sub-project ID #008): access to historical RAN performance monitoring datasets was provided; initial IPSEC VPN connectivity details were shared; target virtualized appliance configuration was discussed and will be implemented in the second phase of the PoC;
- Sub-project “Mobile Augmented Reality for Outdoor PoI (Points of Interest) Enrichment” (sub-project ID #049): access to the ORO commercial 5G network was provided with 2 SIM cards provisioned with the “trials” APN, allowing for direct access to the Bucharest 5G Lab Edge Computing

facility; access to one VM with GPU capabilities was provided; access to the 5G Lab Edge Computing facility was provided throughout a VPN client and account;

- Sub-project “AdaptoFlow” (sub-project ID #042): discussions about the capabilities of the Romanian testbed were undergone in order for the AdaptoFlow team to adapt their target PoC.

No extension to the existing Edge Computing platforms or commercial/private 5G coverage is required.

3.1.5 Romanian cluster (experimental facilities in Belgium)

This section provides a brief overview of infrastructure upgrades that are needed on the 5GOpen testbed (Next-Gen) to support the execution of the sub-project 6GVision (sub-project ID #001) as an Option 1b. This sub-project focuses on a use case scenario in an art gallery that falls into the application domain Culture (vision-aided mmWave communication), aiming to provide support for users with Virtual Reality (VR) helmets to have a seamless service regardless of the obstacles and other museum visitors. The deployment consists of a small cell 5G base station with mmWave (FR2) installed in an indoor environment (e.g., a crowded art gallery). The User Equipment (UE) is an XR device that is blocked by a random visitor of the gallery, and as such suffers strong signal attenuation and connectivity disruption, which requires a proactive handover to another 5G base station with Line of Sight (LoS).

Figure 32. Allbesmart [29] solution for 5G FR2.

To enable trialing of such use case on the 5GOpen testbed, some upgrades are required. First, as mentioned in Section 2.5, the test license has been obtained by IMEC for the mmWave band (400 MHz @ 26.5-26.9 GHz) with EIRP of 14.24W. This license was necessary to obtain before proceeding with the installation and testing of the equipment provided by sub-project participant Allbesmart. Second, the upgrades to the testbed refer to the equipment shown in Figure 32, which consists of the O-RAN compliant computer platform: Central Unit (O-CU) and Distributed Unit (O-DU), for FR2 spectrum. This system will be integrated into the existing 5GOpen testbed, where the existing gNB test network will be extended with a near real-time RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) and a COTS RU operating in FR2. The overall high-level architecture of the upgraded components is shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33. The architecture of 5G gNodeB from FR2 and 5G Core to be integrated with the 5GOpen testbed.

3.1.6 Greek cluster

The sub-project “MILESTONE - A REAL-TIME AIENABLED WORKER SAFETY PRESERVATION SYSTEM” (named MILESTONE, sub-project ID #047) is part of the Greek cluster as an Option 1b and is designed to support surveillance equipment control, as well as continuous monitoring of the working environment using data streamed through the public 5G network. The sub-project adopts a computer vision AI model to make predictions several times per second for each camera/drone (e.g., over 10 times per second to maintain a stable framerate of 10 FPS), as well as real-time control of the surveillance equipment when a safety violation occurs (e.g., the camera zooms or the drone moves closer to the location of interest to get a better view of the situation). In addition, safety supervisors, the end-users of the MILESTONE system, can take advantage of the offered functionalities to obtain real-time insights and alerts regarding worker safety compliance in remote public infrastructure locations through an easy-to-use interface. The architecture adopted by MILESTONE is depicted in Figure 34.

As mentioned earlier, the project uses a public 5G network and does not intervene with the settings of the network. However, the trial itself takes place in Athens area (including Technopolis) as an extension of the UC2 of TrialsNet.

Figure 34. MILESTONE architecture.

3.2 Options 2 sub-projects

The infrastructure used to perform the Option 2 trials cover a variety of network setups listed in Table 2, with a mix of commercial and private deployments aimed at enabling specific services, such as teleoperation, Edge Computing, healthcare, or immersive gaming. The trials involve different network infrastructures depending on the service and geographical location. Annex A reports a detailed description of the Option 2 private infrastructures provided by the concerned sub-projects.

Table 2. Sub-projects Overview.

Sub-project ID	Sub-Project name	Description	Commercial / Private	Hardware/Software components
026	AI4RTC: AI applications for Real-time Charging Load Management	AI-driven real-time communications optimization over 5G networks, focusing on traffic control and latency improvements.	Private	AI-based traffic controllers, Edge Computing devices, 5G routers, software-defined networking.
061	5G AUGMENTED REALITY TOUR FOR THE UNESCO SITE “HISTORICAL CENTER OF NAPLES”	Augmented reality tourist guide using 5G commercial networks in UNESCO sites.	Commercial	Mobile Phones, VR glasses, geolocated AR objects.
029	5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System (5GS3)	Autonomous robotic security systems using private 5G networks in airports.	Private	Private 5G core, autonomous robots, perimeter security systems.
017	5GVIREH: Virtual Reality Enhanced Rehabilitation	Remote healthcare and emergency response using virtual reality and real-time communications over 5G.	Commercial	VR headsets, remote medical devices, 5G core network, real-time data analytics.
055	Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving	Testbed focused on autonomous driving using 5G tele-operation and Edge Computing.	Private	5G CPE, V-Tron [30] tele-operated vehicle, IMEC orchestrator.
028	Beyond 5G Football Stadium	Deployment of 5G network to enhance fan experiences in a football stadium.	Commercial and Private	6 Cells with 4G/5G radios, DU/CU servers, Core Network deployment.
007	“Remember Ascari”: MR in MAUTO – Immersive MR Experience in F1 (MAUTO)	5G network supporting immersive racing experiences.	Commercial	Mixture of 5G and WiFi services
040	Cities Without Barriers	Enabling urban accessibility for people with disabilities through 5G and Edge Computing.	Commercial	RGB cameras, Mobile Phones, cloud computing, AI-based accessibility analysis.

062	CITY4ALL	Commercial public 5G network to create VR experiences for students.	Commercial	VR headsets and tablets connected to the public network.
025	Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations	Monitoring 5G tram operations and conducting tests in Florence with Vodafone.	Commercial and Private	5G antennas, SDR boards, Containerized Software
045	Intelligent control of interconnected manufacturing infrastructures (i-CNC)	Industrial deployment using 5G for real-time data processing in CNC machines.	Commercial	5G CPE, Kubernetes, Grafana, Raspberry Pi.
009	MediVision-5G (eHealth)	5G-enabled healthcare VR applications for surgeons and patients.	Commercial and Private	5G RRU, 5G CPE, MQTT communication, VR headsets.
043	METACLINIC	Remote healthcare applications with 5G, using VR for emergency interventions.	Commercial and Private	Commercial 5G core, VR headsets, Dockerized platform, mmWave antennas.
036	Torino 4U: 10 things to see around you	Mobile app enhancing urban exploration through public 5G networks in Turin.	Commercial	Mobile Phones, cloud servers, public 5G networks.
010	Turin 5Games	Cloud gaming over 5G network for real-time gaming in Turin.	Commercial	XR headsets, cloud gaming platform.

3.2.1 High-level categorization

The Open Call sub-projects leverage the capabilities of 5G to push boundaries in fields such as autonomous driving, healthcare, urban accessibility, and entertainment. These sub-projects generally fall into distinct categories based on their objectives, type of applications, related employed technologies, and infrastructure setups. In the following, a high-level categorization of the Option 2 sub-projects is provided based on the project's domains.

3.2.1.1 ITSS Domain

Autonomous Driving and Smart Transport

The sub-projects ATOS Driving and “Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations” (named Connected Rails) focus on the use of 5G for smart transport solutions. ATOS Driving is centered on a tele-operated vehicle in the Unmanned Valley, Netherlands. It uses a private 5G setup with a private TNO network and Edge Computing to enable real-time remote vehicle control. Connected Rails, on the other hand, focuses on monitoring tramway operations in Florence, using commercial 5G network combined with on-board sensors to collect and process real-time operational data. Both projects rely on URLLC services to ensure the safe and efficient operation of vehicles in controlled environments.

Industrial and Security Applications

Industrial and security-focused sub-projects such as “Intelligent control of interconnected manufacturing infrastructures (i-CNC)” (named i-CNC) and “5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System (5GS3)” (named 5GS3) utilize 5G for highly specific, real-time operational needs. i-CNC is geared towards industrial CNC machining, leveraging a combination of Teltonika routers [31] and Kubernetes clusters to ensure real-time data processing with low latency. 5GS3, on the other hand, focuses on airport security by deploying autonomous robotic security systems, supported by private 5G networks that ensure reliable and fast communication for surveillance and perimeter protection.

3.2.1.2 eHE domain

Healthcare and Remote Assistance

Three Option 2 sub-projects target innovations in healthcare. The sub-projects “MediVision-5G (eHealth)” (named MediVision5G) and METACLINIC are both aimed at leveraging 5G for healthcare applications, especially in critical and remote medical interventions. MediVision5G deploys a compact “5G-in-a-box” solution to enable high-speed, low-latency VR applications for surgeons. Similarly, METACLINIC uses commercial 5G core to provide virtual consultations and emergency medical interventions across different locations, relying on both mmWave and sub-6 GHz frequencies to deliver healthcare services at scale. Both projects prioritize robust, secure communication and low-latency transmission to facilitate remote medical treatments. The sub-project “5GVIREH: Virtual Reality Enhanced Rehabilitation” (named 5GVireh), whose architecture is depicted in Figure 35, focuses on remote healthcare and emergency response, using virtual reality and real-time communications over commercial 5G networks. The setup includes VR headsets and remote medical devices, supported by a 5G core network to enable real-time data analytics and communication during emergencies.

Figure 35. 5GVireh Network Architecture.

3.2.1.3 CTE domain

Urban Accessibility and Smart Cities

The sub-projects “Cities Without Barriers” and “Torino 4U: 10 things to see around you” (named Torino4U) focus on utilizing 5G to enhance urban living, particularly for underserved populations. Cities Without Barriers, deployed in Turin, uses a commercial 5G network to support people with disabilities by enabling real-time video analytics and obstacle detection through Edge Computing. Similarly, Torino4U focuses on enhancing urban exploration through a public 5G network, using mobile applications to provide users with interactive navigation experiences across the city. Both projects emphasize the role of real-time data processing and 5G’s low-latency characteristics in improving the quality of life in urban environments. The sub-project “AI4RTC: AI applications for Real-time Charging Load Management” (named AI4RTC) is centered on AI-driven real-time communication optimization over 5G networks. It uses a private network and focuses on traffic control and latency improvements through AI-based traffic controllers, Edge Computing devices, and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) solutions.

Entertainment, Tourism, and Gaming

A significant number of TrialsNet sub-projects focus on enhancing user experiences in entertainment and tourism via 5G. The sub-projects “Beyond 5G Football Stadium” and “Remember Ascari: MR in MAUTO - Immersive MR Experience in F1 (MAUTO)” (named Black Cats and Checkered Flags) leverage on 5G in stadium

and racing environments. Beyond 5G Football Stadium deploys both private and public 5G networks in an Israeli stadium to support fan engagement and operational efficiency. Black Cats and Checkered Flags uses 5G technology combined with Wi-Fi 6 to deliver immersive racing experiences, focusing on low-latency communication for real-time interactivity. In a similar way, the sub-projects “Turin5Games” and “5G AUGMENTED REALITY TOUR FOR THE UNESCO SITE - HISTORICAL CENTER OF NAPLES” (named 5G Naples UNESCO AR Tour) focus on immersive experiences through gaming and tourism. Turin5Games explores cloud gaming over 5G networks, optimizing XR devices for low-latency gaming, while 5G Naples UNESCO AR Tour uses 5G to offer interactive AR experiences to tourists exploring UNESCO heritage sites.

Education and VR Learning

Finally, CITY4ALL focuses on utilizing commercial 5G networks for education, creating immersive virtual reality (VR) experiences for students. By providing real-time interactions in educational settings via commercial 5G network, CITY4ALL seeks to enhance learning outcomes through interactive content delivered to VR headsets and tablets.

3.2.2 Network deployment

The TrialsNet sub-projects demonstrate diverse approaches to device connectivity, largely shaped by whether they rely on commercial 5G networks or private network deployments. The following subsections highlights the equipment and connectivity for the different use cases.

3.2.2.1 Commercial 5G Networks

Sub-projects that use commercial 5G networks benefit from the existing infrastructure provided by established carriers, which is particularly effective in urban and high-traffic environments. For example, the Cities Without Barriers project in Turin uses the city’s commercial 5G network to connect RGB cameras and smartphones. These devices upload real-time video data to the cloud, where Edge Computing processes it for urban accessibility solutions. Similarly, Torino4U uses public 5G networks to connect smartphones running a mobile app that enhances urban exploration through real-time navigation and user interaction.

In the Beyond 5G Football Stadium project, a combination of public and private networks supports fan engagement and operational efficiency. Smartphones, sensors, and fan engagement devices leverage both commercial and private 5G networks for real-time data exchange during stadium events. Black Cats and Checkered Flags uses a commercial 5G network, supported by Wi-Fi 6, to provide immersive racing experiences. Devices such as MetaQuest 3 [32] VR headsets connect via this network to deliver high-speed, low-latency communication essential for real-time racing simulations.

Tourism and gaming applications also rely on commercial 5G networks. The 5G Naples UNESCO AR Tour project provides augmented reality experiences to tourists, using smartphones and AR glasses connected to commercial 5G networks. Similarly, Turin5Games focuses on cloud gaming over TIM’s commercial 5G NSA network, where XR headsets and gaming controllers are used for real-time gaming experiences. Lastly, the CITY4ALL project uses commercial 5G network to support educational VR experiences, where students use VR headsets and tablets to access interactive learning environments. Similarly, 5GVireh operates within healthcare facilities using commercial 5G networks to support remote medical devices and VR headsets for emergency response. This setup ensures the real-time transmission of critical data from remote medical devices to healthcare professionals.

3.2.2.2 Private network infrastructure

In contrast, sub-projects relying on private networks often do so to maintain stringent control over performance, latency, and security, particularly in industrial or remote settings. For instance, the ATOS Driving sub-project, relies on a private 5G network managed by TNO’s B5G core. Tele-operated vehicles equipped with V-Tron technology and 5G routers are connected to this network, ensuring ultra-reliable communication for remote vehicle control. Similarly, Connected Rails (Figure 36) combines commercial 5G network with a sandbox testing environment in a controlled environment. Sensors onboard Florence’s tram system transmit real-time operational data to the cloud, ensuring safe and efficient tram operations.

AI4RTC also leverages a private network to optimize real-time communications with the help of AI-driven traffic control systems. The project operates in a controlled test environment, using private 5G setups to improve latency and traffic management, allowing AI-based controllers to fine-tune network performance in real time.

In industrial contexts, the i-CNC project uses commercial 5G network with private extensions to connect CNC machines via Teltonika routers. These machines transmit real-time operational data to ensure precision and efficiency in machining processes. Healthcare projects like MediVision5G and METACLINIC also leverage on a private network setups. MediVision5G employs a compact “5G-in-a-box” solution to connect VR headsets through remote radio units (RRUs) and CPE devices, ensuring low-latency performance for medical applications. Similarly, METACLINIC uses private 5G network combined with mmWave technology to enable high-speed data transfer for remote healthcare interventions.

In the 5GS3 project, private 5G networks are deployed to operate autonomous robotic security systems at airports. These systems rely on secure and reliable connections for real-time monitoring and perimeter security, using autonomous robots equipped with sensors that communicate over the private 5G network.

Figure 36. Connected Rails Network Setup.

3.2.3 Deployment areas

The deployment areas of the TrialsNet sub-projects reflect the diversity of use cases across different environments, ranging from urban centers to rural testbeds. The scale and scope of deployment vary significantly, with projects addressing both small, localized deployments and larger, expansive setups.

3.2.3.1 Urban deployments

Several sub-projects are focused on urban areas, where the high density of users and infrastructure can fully leverage the benefits of 5G. For example, Cities Without Barriers takes place in Turin, an urban setting where accessibility improvements for people with disabilities are a priority. This project uses the city's existing 5G infrastructure to provide real-time navigation assistance through smartphones and cameras, focusing on high-traffic areas such as pedestrian zones and public transportation hubs.

Similarly, Torino4U is an urban-focused project that enhances city exploration through mobile applications connected to public 5G networks. This deployment covers various parts of the city, allowing users to interact with urban landmarks and attractions in real time. The scale is smaller, targeting individual users in specific locations, but the impact is broader as it aims to improve urban navigation and experience.

Beyond 5G Football Stadium represents a large-scale urban deployment in a sports and entertainment context. Located in an Israeli football stadium, this project supports thousands of fans through a mix of public and private 5G networks, enabling real-time engagement, media streaming, and operational efficiency. The high-density environment of the stadium showcases 5G's ability to handle large volumes of data traffic in confined, high-demand spaces.

Turin5Games and 5G Naples UNESCO AR Tour are also urban-focused deployments, although their target scenarios differ. Turin5Games operates in Turin's urban area and involves cloud gaming experiences powered by 5G, focusing on the entertainment sector. In contrast, 5G Naples UNESCO AR Tour targets the tourism sector, deploying 5G-connected AR glasses and smartphones to enhance cultural experiences at UNESCO heritage sites located in urban settings.

The CITY4ALL project also falls into the urban deployment category, focusing on education within urban environments. Using commercial 5G network, this project brings immersive VR educational experiences to schools, enabling interactive learning experiences in classrooms across cities.

5GVireh, another urban-focused deployment, operates in healthcare facilities where it provides virtual reality-based healthcare and emergency response services. The project leverages commercial 5G networks to enable real-time data transmission from remote medical devices, ensuring that healthcare professionals can access critical patient information in real-time, even in emergencies.

3.2.3.2 Rural and remote deployments

Some sub-projects take place in rural or controlled remote environments, often where the absence of existing infrastructure requires specialized, private network setups. The ATOS Driving sub-project is deployed in a rural, controlled testbed in the Netherlands. This project focuses on autonomous vehicle tele-operation and Edge Computing, where the rural environment simulates highway scenarios and remote driving conditions. The large-scale nature of the deployment allows for extensive testing over various terrains and conditions, without the interference typical of urban environments.

Similarly, Connected Rails takes place on tramways in Florence, but also incorporates a rural aspect in its sandbox testing environment at UPC [33] labs. Here, controlled conditions allow for rigorous testing of 5G connectivity in transportation before deployment in urban rail networks.

The sub-project Black Cats and Checkered Flags is deployed in a rural setting, focusing on a racetrack environment where immersive 5G experiences are delivered to users in real time. This project takes advantage of the open space and lower interference found in rural areas, enabling smoother, uninterrupted racing simulations and immersive user experiences on a smaller scale.

3.2.3.3 Smaller-scale deployments

Several sub-projects involve smaller-scale deployments, where the focus is on testing the efficacy of 5G in localized or specific use cases. For instance, i-CNC is an industrial deployment centered on a single CNC machining operation. The deployment is small in scope but critical in ensuring that real-time data can be processed with minimal latency, improving manufacturing processes. This smaller, contained deployment is typical for industrial settings, where precise control over the environment is required.

MediVision5G is another example of a smaller-scale deployment, focused on healthcare environments. The project is deployed within hospital settings or localized healthcare facilities, where VR headsets and medical devices connect to private 5G networks to facilitate remote surgical procedures and patient care. Despite being small in scale, the stakes are high, as the healthcare scenario demands ultra-reliable, low-latency communication.

AI4RTC is a smaller-scale deployment focused on AI-driven real-time communications optimization. The project operates within a controlled environment, using a private network to improve traffic control and reduce latency in communication processes. This setup allows AI-based traffic controllers to fine-tune network performance and enhance communication reliability in real-time scenarios.

3.2.3.4 Larger-scale and complex deployments

On the opposite end, projects like 5GS3 represent large-scale, complex deployments. This project is focused on security and is deployed across a vast area at Athens International Airport. Autonomous robots and security systems connect over private 5G networks to manage perimeter security in real-time, requiring extensive coverage and reliability across the airport's complex infrastructure. This large-scale deployment highlights the capabilities of 5G in managing critical infrastructure over a wide area.

Beyond 5G Football Stadium (depicted in Figure 37) also stands out as a large-scale deployment, involving thousands of users and a mix of public and private 5G networks. The project is not only large in terms of user density but also in its operational scope, as it must maintain high-quality connectivity for numerous simultaneous activities, from fan engagement to media streaming.

Figure 37. Beyond 5G football stadium network deployment.

3.2.3.5 Targeted deployment scenarios

In terms of specific target scenarios, sub-projects like ATOS Driving and Connected Rails are focused on transportation and mobility. The rural testbed of ATOS Driving simulates highways and remote vehicle operations, while Connected Rails focuses on tramway operations within urban and test environments. These projects address the mobility challenges of the future, utilizing 5G to enable safer, more efficient transportation.

Healthcare-oriented projects such as MediVision5G and METACLINIC target hospital and emergency scenarios. These deployments are highly focused on ensuring that medical staff can deliver remote healthcare services with the necessary speed and reliability, particularly in emergency situations or remote locations.

Entertainment and tourism are targeted by projects like Turin5Games, Black Cats and Checkered Flags, and 5G Naples UNESCO AR Tour. These deployments focus on enhancing user experiences through immersive gaming, sports, and cultural interactions, with 5G enabling real-time, high-bandwidth communication to support these applications.

4 Security Handbook

Network and devices security is a critical topic to be considered when a system relies on 5G and B5G technologies. This section outlines the security measures implemented across the TrialsNet site infrastructures, spanning across the different network segments and entities from the Cloud and Virtualization infrastructure to the devices (e.g., CPEs). This section aims also to summarize the security technologies that external experimenters are dealing with and that have to meet in order to deploy the use cases' applications during the trial periods.

4.1 Italian cluster (Turin site)

Table 3 reports the description of the security aspects for the Italian cluster, Turin site.

Table 3. Italian cluster (Turin site) security aspects.

Security Topic	Description
Cloud & Virtualization Security	The Italian site includes a cluster of physical servers, with two virtualization tools on top of them. To deploy containerized applications, an instance of K8s has been deployed, while for de-ployment VNF-based applications an instance of Openstack is available. Each of these technologies has its built-in security technology to expose secure interfaces to the users. In particular: (i) in OpenStack, security is managed by the Keystone submodule [34], (ii) in k8s, APIs of the kube-apiserver [35] are exposed through HTTPS
Edge Security	The Turin site doesn't make use of Edge Devices
Far Edge & IoT Security	Far Edge and IoT devices are equipped with SIM cards for connecting them via 5G to private APNs
Network Security	The network security at commercial network level is implemented by TIM policies, including the Core Network. By the usage of APN, the traffic is segregated on a private subnet in the TIM lab and connected via dark fiber to the cloud environment hosted at PoliTO. Both organizations (TIM and CNIT/PoliTO) manage the security of their internal network by firewall and proxy, managed by specific departments, external users are authenticated by VPN mechanism.
Trial Security	User and devices authentication is ensured at each layer of the trial applications, as well as data protection.

4.2 Italian cluster (Pisa site)

Table 4 reports the description of the security aspects for the Italian cluster, Pisa site.

Table 4. Italian cluster (Pisa site) security aspects.

Security Topic	Description
Cloud & Virtualization Security	Ericsson's cloud platforms use a Zero Trust model, where no device, network, or application is inherently trusted. Every access request must be authenticated, verified, and encrypted. End-to-end encryption protocols ensure that data remains confidential from the user device to the application server. The COMO5 server will adopt state-of-the art security features to secure access to the server. The server will have a firewall installed

	<p>allowing only SSH remote connections and access to a web dashboard. Remote SSH connection for management will be allowed only via RSA-key authentication, while password authentication will be disabled, in addition access will be granted only from a selection of authorized IP addresses from the University of Pisa. The dashboard for the clinician will be exposed using only HTTPS, allowing connection only to authenticated users.</p>
Edge Security	<p>Ericsson systems used for the trial provides security and compliance auditing at the Edge, ensuring that the distributed Edge nodes natively meet regulatory and security standards</p>
Far Edge & IoT Security	<p>Data exchanged over the air between the device (i.e., User Equipment) and the radio base station (antenna side) is natively encrypted using advanced cryptographic algorithms. Ericsson systems used in the trial ensures both confidentiality and integrity of the data coming from the Edge devices to prevent interception.</p> <p>Sensitive healthcare data originated by IoT devices (smart watches, AR/VR glasses, diagnostic systems) are segmented from non-sensitive data using secured wired VLANs or wireless network slices in 5G, ensuring it cannot be accessed by unauthorized devices or services.</p> <p>COMO5 devices will not be exposed to Internet access and only traffic to the COMO5 server for data collection and analysis will be authorized.</p>
Network Security	<p>The network is separated and dedicated to the trial (dedicated spectrum non used for commercial traffic, dedicated apparatus in RAN and UPF, the CN is not used for commercial traffic, SIM dedicated to the trial and not used for commercial scope).</p> <p>Network slicing technique is used in the 5G network deployed in the trial to allow the single physical network to be divided into multiple “virtual networks”, each tailored to specific requirements and use cases. The segmentation and isolation in slices ensure that even if one slice is compromised, it doesn't affect the others. Ericsson’s baseband unit used in the trial segregates traffic across different network slices, ensuring that any compromise in one slice doesn’t affect the rest of the network.</p> <p>Security for connection across Pisa-Torino is assured by secured VPN. Both organizations (TIM and CNR) manage the security of their internal network by firewall and proxy, managed by specific departments, external users are authenticated by VPN mechanism. The connection Pisa-Massa is ensured by dedicated fiber.</p>
Trial Security	<p>Access to the overall CNR campus is monitored by human controlled access and CCTV while access to the trial rooms is monitored by cameras and restricted based on responsibilities, and even then, access is only granted during specific time windows when the experimentations are planned.</p> <p>The baseband processing systems and the servers running cloud applications are housed in dedicated racks within the server room of the CNR campus, which has an additional level of security as access to the area is granted only through electronic authentication (badge). Core network is hosted in TIM premises that is monitored by human controlled access and CCTV. The access to room hosted the core</p>

	network is monitored by cameras and restricted based on responsibilities, and even then, access is only granted during specific time windows. Furthermore, a secure remote access is assured by TIM policies.
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4.3 Spanish cluster

Table 5 reports the description of the security aspects for the Spanish cluster.

Table 5. Spanish cluster security aspects.

Security Topic	Description
Cloud & Virtualization Security	There is controlled access to the datacenter in 5Tonic Premises with 24h surveillance and fingerprint access. The datacenter has firewall and SSH-only access in place. Remote access can be done through VPN server that provides individual user access, without the use of generic accounts
Edge Security	Ericsson systems used for the trial provides security and compliance auditing at the Edge. The Flight Rack is currently located in a secure lab, with fingerprint access and 24h surveillance, with VPN access available only through SSH.
Far Edge & IoT Security	Data flow in the air interface (between the CPE and the Radio) is encrypted by default. Data Centric Private network is in place, meaning that access to the network can be done only with specific provisioned SIM cards. Furthermore, the number of commercially available FR2-mmwave only devices is very low, which makes more difficult to access the 5G network for unwanted devices.
Network Security	There is a VPN in place between the Edge equipment and the Core network. No specific slices are to be used in this setup, since most of the traffic will be carried in the local UPF and the traffic type is similar during the test execution.
Trial Security	The RAN + UPF Flight Rack will be located in a secure location during the trial, with no access to the general public. The rest of the equipment will be installed in rooms with controlled access and will be always under supervision of the Use Case participants. 24h video surveillance as well as private security are in place in the venue

4.4 Romanian cluster

Table 6 reports the description of the security aspects for the Romanian cluster.

Table 6. Romanian cluster security aspects.

Security Topic	Description
Cloud & Virtualization Security	The Cloud and Virtualization Security of the Romanian cluster is implemented using the following systems: controlled access to the Bucharest and Iasi datacenters through specifically provisioned identity cards; access control to the virtualized infrastructure (OpenStack, VMware vSphere, Kubernetes) management platforms through dedicated IAM/PAM systems; Fortinet firewalls to filter the inbound and outbound traffic coming from the commercial network

	(over the project dedicated APN), the 5G SA devices, the Bucharest and Iasi 5G Labs Edge Computing facilities and the VPN users.
Edge Security	Not applicable.
Far Edge & IoT Security	Regarding the Far Edge and IoT Security of the Romanian cluster, it is implemented using a private TrialsNet-project specific APN, that is provisioned on a limited number of SIM cards (6 pieces), installed in the 5G CPEs that are installed in the city of Iasi (password protected) and that are directly connected to the Bucharest 5G Lab Edge Computing facility. The data traffic flowing in/out of the APN is continuously monitored by the 5G Lab firewall and only a specific set of ports are allowed for communications.
Network Security	The topic of Network Security is especially important in the context of ORO's 5G Lab private 5G SA network deployment, as the commercial network is secured by design. For the private network, a specific slice is already configured for the Iasi radio cells and remote UPF. This slice is assuring the data traffic isolation from the rest of the network, this being especially useful in the context of the sensitive data travelling the network from the surveillance cameras placed in the city to the Iasi 5G Lab Edge Computing facility.
Trial Security	Regarding the Trial Security, several aspects detailed in the previous sections are key for the E2E security of the UC1 and UC4 application pilots that are currently ongoing in Iasi. Therefore, physical security of the datacenter hosting the video analytics application server is assuring that no unauthorized user is getting access to the raw data feeds. Moreover, the server that is hosting the application is protected using authorization mechanisms and cannot be accessed by people that don't know the credentials. Furthermore, the raw data feeds coming from the surveillance cameras are only kept for the duration of the video analytics algorithms run (implementing also video stream anonymization) and are not stored.

4.5 Romanian cluster (experimental facilities in Belgium)

Table 7 reports the description of the security aspects for the experimental facilities in Belgium.

Table 7. Belgian experimental facilities security aspects.

Security Topic	Description
Cloud & Virtualization Security	Currently, user authentication is used for accessing the resources in the testbed. In addition, all testbed components are behind a firewall that only allows outside access via VPN. In the near future, IMEC will be federating the testbed into the SLICES [36] federation of testbeds, at which point the user authentication, remote access & experiment isolation mechanisms will be further enhanced.
Edge Security	The Edge Computing infrastructure refers to the RSUs in the Smart Highway testbed. The same mechanisms are applied as for the Cloud security.
Far Edge & IoT Security	The far Edge and IoT infrastructure is deployed on the OBUs of the test vehicles within the Smart Highway testbed. These resources are also placed behind a firewall, and user needs a VPN access to the testbed to reach the far Edge infrastructure and deploy/use services.

Network Security	Currently, all testbed components are connected to a control network that is protected by a firewall that only allows outside access via VPN. When testbed users use the infrastructure to set up their own 5G network, they are responsible for the security in that network. Concerning the 5GOpen testbed, network security mechanism from the OAI solution stack are deployed on the radio, and Free5GC on the 5G Core. In addition, the isolation of network resources is available through the creation of slices: Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency (URLLC) and Best-effort (BE), which is a default slice with a limited resource pool. Whether or not slicing is used, is up to the testbed user. In the near future, IMEC will be federating the testbed into the SLICES federation of testbeds, at which point IMEC will further enhance the network security of the testbed by, amongst others, allowing testbed users to create private VLANs between specific nodes / VMs / Containers to isolate their own traffic from the control subnet.
Trial Security	Currently, a combination of user authentication, firewalling and VPNs is used to control who has access to the testbed infrastructure. As mentioned previously, IMEC will soon proceed with the federation of the testbed within the SLICES framework, at which point further enhancements of the authentication, remote access & experiment isolation capabilities of the testbed are expected.

4.6 Greek cluster

Table 8 reports the description of the security aspects for the Greek cluster.

Table 8. Greek cluster security aspects.

Security Topic	Description
Cloud & Virtualization Security	User authentication plays an important role in ensuring secure access to network services deployed within the WINGS cloud environment. This process verifies the identity of users, giving access only to authorized users and safeguarding sensitive resources. In addition to authentication, the infrastructure components are fortified with an added layer of security by being positioned behind a firewall. This combination of authentication protocols and firewall protection helps mitigate potential cyber threats, ensuring that the network services and infrastructure remain secure and operational in the cloud ecosystem.
Edge Security	Not Applicable
Far Edge & IoT Security	To ensure secure communication between end-users and the WINGS cloud, a combination of user authentication and the HTTPS protocol is used. User authentication verifies the identity of individuals accessing the system, while the HTTPS protocol encrypts data in transit. This dual approach ensures that sensitive information remains protected during interactions with the cloud environment. Furthermore, the underlying infrastructure components are secured by being placed behind a robust firewall, adding another layer of defense against unauthorized access and cyber threats. Together, these measures provide a comprehensive security framework for the WINGS cloud

Network Security	The network is secured through the implementation of firewalls and access rules, which work together to restrict unauthorized entry and ensure that only permitted users or systems can interact with the infrastructure. However, it is important to note that network slices, which are virtualized, isolated segments of a network designed to optimize resource allocation and performance for specific use cases, are not utilized in this setup.
Trial Security	This is similar to Far Edge & IoT Security description mentioned above.

5 Development status and preliminary results of TrialsNet Innovations

This section presents the ongoing development and preliminary results of innovations introduced in the TrialsNet project. These innovations are categorized into horizontal and vertical types, addressing both broad, foundational technologies like ZSM and specific application-oriented advancements tailored to individual use cases. This section highlights how these innovations enhance the platform's functionality, expand its capabilities, and align with the project's overarching goals.

5.1 Horizontal Innovations

5.1.1 Zero-touch Service Management

The Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) Proof-of-Concept (PoC) serves as a versatile framework capable of supporting multiple use cases dynamically and simultaneously within a network. It can be deployed across various network regions such as the Core or the Edge for strategic placement. This cross-domain approach guides the implementation of flexible and dynamic solutions that are compatible with multiple Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) environments, ensuring adaptability to diverse technological needs and reducing the need for human intervention by enabling near real-time, asynchronous, technology-agnostic, and distributed implementations across domains. The general research outcomes, and the design principles related to ZSM have been already presented in detail in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2]. This section focuses on the deployment progress and integration activities performed within WP2.

5.1.1.1 Cross-domain ZSM integration

The ZSM framework enables various NFVIs to provide metrics in a standardized format, facilitating integration in variable environments. The ZSM framework can be configured as a distributed or dedicated deployment for specific scenarios with very low or no manual configuration as shown in Figure 38. In the Smart Highway testbed, it is divided into two sections with different priorities. The first section focuses on end-to-end (E2E) latency for mission-critical applications (such as UC4 application interacting with the VRUs), particularly where vehicular traffic is relevant. The second section prioritizes lower power consumption, suitable for light traffic conditions. Both sections allow decision-making processes to handle multiple sets of metrics simultaneously based on their priorities.

Figure 38. ZSM Framework and NFVIs Configurations.

This supports the combination of diverse resources like presented in Figure 39 and Figure 40 with the integration of the Smart Highway testbed and Nextworks NFVI, regardless of their technology stack, as long as the metric messages are sent in a structured and standardized format. Its functions can be intertwined with AI/ML techniques for decision-making but also for predictions based on the priorities of each use case scenario, which can grow in complexity, e.g., a section of a highway that has a large area that for instance contains a large number of roadside units (RSUs).

Figure 39. ZSM Framework components for cross-domain integration.

Figure 40. NextWorks LCM platform and Smart Highway testbed ZSM Integration.

5.1.1.2 Standardization and automation of ZSM

As the orchestrator of the ZSM Framework can incorporate different platform sources simultaneously, integration has been made between the Smart Highway testbed and the Nextworks Life Cycle Management (LCM) platform as illustrated in Figure 39 and Figure 40. The status of the ZSM orchestration can be inspected near real-time in the ZSM Dashboard Control like depicted in Figure 41 and Figure 42. The ZSM orchestrator collects and groups the metrics by their platform of origin and makes the decisions independently for each group of

metrics. For the orchestrator no extra or manual configuration is required, as each platform is responsible for sending a small but crucial description of their setup:

- **Name:** identifies the platform, the orchestrator uses it as a tag to group the metrics by origin.
- **Location:** GPS coordinates used to display the nodes in a map, but also to be used for decision-making in mobility use case scenarios.
- **Monitoring topic:** the pub Zenoh-styled topic to listen to for the metrics.
- **Deployment topic:** the Zenoh-styled topic where the decisions are sent to be executed.
- **Priorities set:** the order of priority of the metrics sent to the orchestrator in which the values are sorted for decision-making, it varies according to the conditions of the use case where the following have different impact: E2E latency, performance or power consumption.

Figure 41. Architecture of the ZSM Central Live Dashboard Demo.

Figure 42. ZSM Central Live Dashboard Control.

The monitoring process is carried out using Zenoh as pub/sub messaging tool due to its low overhead load and its discovery feature that makes the entities to be monitored like nodes, to be detected without further configuration of static addresses. This brings high flexibility both for the installation of the ZSM framework and the subscription/un-subscription of an entity to the ZSM orchestrator. The decision-making process is enabled by both policy-driven and inference to a DRL agent that has been trained with the historical data. The data set can be persistently stored as plain text files that are dynamically grouped by datetime-named folder, or in a database. No extra configuration to the database is needed as the ZSM orchestrator subscribe each new incoming node and its metrics. The data sent by the publisher has to be normalized in the following structure:

- **Origin:** the name of the node or the entity that is being monitored, usually the hostname.
- **IP:** local IP address in the case of the smart highway for E2E latency checks.
- **Metric type:** the kind of metric that is being sent, it will be matched with the priority set during the decision-making process.
- **Value:** the value of the metric that is being sent.
- **Setup:** the description of the setup of origin for grouping the data according to the platform of origin.

The history of the decisions and the metrics are distributed in a different table per metric type, but in a snapshot table that compiles the latest status of all the metrics per node. Depending on each platform, the type of metrics can differ and it is not an issue for data collection as the matching process for priority and metric type is dynamic. In the case of the Smart Highway, vehicular services are running in dedicated pods of K8s clusters implemented in the RSUs on top of 4km of the E13 highway in Antwerp, Belgium. These services are being monitored and managed by the ZSM orchestrator. Each node publishes metrics from computing resources like CPU, memory and storage and other values like location and power consumption. To measure E2E latency, a latency checker is running in an OBU, and takes dynamically the IP address of the nodes subscribed to the orchestrator. A deployer receives the decisions made by the orchestrator to manage the services that are running in the Smart Highway, such like instantiate, escalate, migrate or terminate. This deployer as every deployer that is subscribed to the ZSM orchestrator, is implemented as a distributed system independently from the orchestrator. This makes the orchestrator platform agnostic and increases the flexibility and scalability of the ZSM framework.

5.1.1.3 Smart Highway ZSM flow

The Smart Highway ZSM flow outlines a sequence of interdependent steps, each contributing to the optimization of network resources and enhancing performance in dynamic highway scenarios. Through these steps, the ZSM Framework showcases the integration of monitoring of computing resources and end-to-end based on publishers and subscribers, and decision-making algorithms.

- **Step 1:** The publisher module of the hosting RSUs sends status values about performance status such as CPU load and Memory use. The dataset also hosts identification properties.
- **Step 2:** The RSUs subscription pool includes the newly arrived RSU identity and shares it with the rest of the applications involved in the PoC.
- **Step 3:** The OBU performs E2E latency checks among the RSUs.
- **Step 4:** The decision-making algorithm processes the datasets sent by the publisher module from the RSUs and the OBU, making choices on the most suitable RSU based on the availability of its resources. The resulting decisions are stored and used to train a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based decision-making algorithm.
- **Step 5:** The stress-inducing scheduler application sends requests to a random RSU that is periodically selected from the manifest shared by the subscription tool. This task is performed to emulate the behavior of the dynamic changes in demand of vehicular network resources, which trigger actions in the orchestration operations for balancing and adjusting the running services.

5.1.1.4 ZSM flow in integration with Nextworks

Nextworks provides its own LCM interface for managing services that can be instantiated through their infrastructure based on K8s. For integration with the Nextworks platform as depicted in Figure 43, their VPN and LCM APIs were utilized. A monitoring and credential library were developed to translate metric values into the standardized format required by the framework. These libraries serve as interface to the Nextworks platform and sends the collected metrics to the ZSM orchestrator. These also work as interfaces for the execution of the decisions by managing the deployed services. The credentials library keeps up the validity of token

authentication with Nextworks platform for a seamless integration beyond the Smart Highway testbed as illustrated in Figure 43. A latency checker service was used to determine the E2E latency of the services deployed in four nodes. As Nextworks inner NVFI is based on K8s implementations, computing performance metrics of their nodes have been obtained.

Figure 43. Nextworks -ZSM Framework integration flow.

5.1.1.5 Installation requirements

The ZSM framework operates within the following technology stack:

- **Ubuntu 22.04** [37]: as operating system.
- **Kubernetes 8** [38]: deployment environment for the services.
- **Zenoh 1.0 library** [39]: pub/sub messaging tool to send and receive metrics and decisions. It is possible the need of installing a zenoh router to bridge the monitoring and orchestration functions, depending on the network topology and firewall configuration of the setup.
- **Python 3.12** [40]: as programming language the orchestrator and AI/ML function libraries.
- **PostgreSQL 16** [41]: is the relational database for storing and retrieving data. It is optional as its use can be turned off in the configuration file.
- **.NET 8 SDK** [42]: linux implementation of .net libraries for the dashboard's API.
- **Blazor and SignalR (8 SDK)** [42]: is already included in the framework of .NET and are used for live monitoring in a dashboard.
- **ZSM Orchestrator Dashboard (PoC implementation)**: uses a configuration file that defines where the dashboard is going to be served and the location and use of the database. This app should be running as a service.

Checklist for initializing and starting ZSM Framework:

- **Check 1:** Check postgres service running status (optional).
- **Check 2:** Check blazorapp.service running status.
- **Check 3:** Start subscriber for the ZSM orchestrator.
- **Check 4:** Start latency checker (optional).
- **Check 5:** Start monitoring in the respective NVFI.

The ZSM orchestrator should automatically recognize the incoming data from the metrics published by the monitoring tools.

5.1.1.6 Results

One of the main results was the ability to simultaneously monitor two different infrastructures within a single framework. In the case of the Smart Highway, it was observed that the orchestrator scaled or migrated services based on resource needs. In the Nextworks platform, the system demonstrated its capability to migrate services similarly, thus optimizing performance and resource utilization. Looking ahead, there are plans to incorporate additional metrics, such as network traffic and energy consumption, and to train an optimization algorithm to enhance decision-making based on those new metrics.

5.1.2 B5G applications framework

This Horizontal innovation is further progressed upon in the context of energy-aware application design for B5G/6G networks. The progress is now focused on embedding the energy-awareness in the application logic and standardizing this approach in the form of an overarching application package, which was previously described in B5G application framework in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2]. Therefore, the updates on this innovation are reported in Section 6.3.

5.1.3 Digital Twins applied to next generation mobile network

The work reported in Section 3.1.3 of D2.2 [2] concluded the analysis of the digital twin support for a selection of vRAN functionalities (i.e., FEC decoding). For the next deliverable, it will be included how digital twins can fit the overall vRAN architecture, for instance O-RAN based ones.

5.2 Vertical Innovations

5.2.1 AI mechanisms for diagnostics and resources efficiency

6G will support the delivery of solutions for verticals which will rely on various distributed AI components in the infrastructure. TrialsNet conducts work on enhanced AI mechanisms framework to assure that the proper performance is delivered by different segments of the 5G/B5G infrastructure (often assuming that some segments are a “closed box”) while monitoring the vertical components with respect to their functional and non-functional behavior to ensure compliance with the requirements. Framed in this context, in UC2 the following developments have taken place:

- **AI Module Integration:** Depending on the use case a specific intelligence module is activated to process the video feed (frames from a camera) and make any necessary detections and calculations. For example, for the road damage use case, it detects various types of damages and calculates their severity. As the sequence of images (video/stream) is given as an input, every frame passes through the Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) Algorithm. This algorithm is used to improve the contrast of the image. An object detection model based on the YOLOv8 [43] architecture is built. This model can detect multiple objects in a single image. The analysis of a video/stream is therefore performed frame-by-frame. The preprocessed frame is given as an input to the model and the detections are the output of the model. For each individual input frame, the detected damage’s cropped image and the damage’s class are collected along with the frame ID and frame shape. For a configurable frame window, this information is collected and passed to the postprocessing stage.
- **Development Operations (DevOps):** Development of each component took place as a dockerised services for ease of deployment of the services using latest technologies such as docker and docker compose inside a Virtual Machine (VM). There are various deployment strategies such as dev, staging and production for different computer environment requirements. Resource efficiency in virtual machines is important and is investigated.
- **Analytics and Diagnostics:** Various analytics are used for assessing the condition of the pavement and identify damage through image processing. For this purpose, after receiving the video source as input, object detection is performed to identify roadway damage and corrective interventions. After the damage is collected for a specific area of the road (e.g., one kilometer), a second level of analysis is

performed to assign a level of severity to the damage in that area. This will give a representative picture of the structural condition of the area.

Moreover, in UC11 the following developments have taken place:

- **AI Module Integration:** Depending on the use case a specific intelligence module is activated to process the video feed (frames from a camera) and make any necessary detections and calculations. For example, for human detection in the context of UC11, it monitors crowd congestion and flow in crowded areas, while tracking also the flows in order to be able to perform a second level of analysis to produce multiple statistics that give a representative picture of the crowd concentration and flow. An object detection model based on the YOLOv8 architecture has been constructed. This model can detect multiple objects in a single image.
- **Analytics and Diagnostics:** Analytics are used for assessing crowd concentration through image processing. For this purpose. The analysis of a video/stream is, therefore, performed frame-by-frame. The frame is given as an input to the model and the detections are the output of the model. For the purpose of UC11, silhouettes of persons (not personal characteristics) are only detected.

5.2.2 Automatic orchestration of network slices to ensure QoS in mobility

The design of the orchestrator functions, as described in D2.2 [2], has been finalized. The orchestrator is capable of concurrently supporting several use cases (UC7, UC8, and U9), including the use case from the open call (i.e., COMO5). Additionally, disturbance traffic will be considered to test the use cases under conditions where traffic of varying priorities coexists in the network.

To ensure the requested E2E QoS, the assignment of the 5G QoS Identifier (5QI) and QoS on the transport network (DSCP) has been clearly defined and assigned to each service (use case). In comparison to current 5G solutions, the following extensions have been incorporated into the design:

- The transport network configuration is linked to the 5QI configuration in RAN/CN which is defined during the provisioning phase of the service.
- The E2E service is associated with the QI/DSCP.
- An admission control mechanism has been included in the transport to manage traffic congestion.
- Additional mechanisms have been integrated into the orchestrator to allow a service to dynamically modify its association with QI/DSCP in the RAN/CN and transport network, respectively.

The orchestration of the transport part has been defined, and its implementation is ongoing. The transport functions in the orchestrator have been tested, and preliminary results show that the admission control and dynamic configuration of the transport nodes are functioning effectively. More details will be reported in the final deliverable D2.4.

5.2.3 Cellular network information for crowd and traffic monitoring

As an alternative to crowd or traffic monitoring solutions based on video surveillance cameras, ORO is internally developing a proprietary solution based on the signalling data coming from the commercial cellular network. The high-level architecture of ORO's cellular data analytics solution was showcased in the previous WP2 D2.2 [2] deliverable and was not updated in the meantime.

Following the preliminary tests of the solution, showcased in D2.2 [2], and concomitantly with the 2024 Sf. Parascheva field trials on-going that were performed using video cameras connected over 5G, ORO recorded again the cellular signaling data from the Iasi area. Based on the analysis of the gathered data, using the procedures described in the previous WP2 deliverable, ORO prepared a comprehensive report regarding the people dynamics for the period between 8 and 22 October 2024, including the religious event that was officially celebrated on 14th of October and will be reported in the next deliverable D2.4.

6 Updates on TrialsNet sustainability solutions from the infrastructure perspective

This chapter provides updates on sustainability solutions within the TrialsNet project, focusing on energy harvesting, utilization, and energy-aware application design. It explores the development of models and frameworks aimed at optimizing energy consumption and integrating renewable energy sources, with an emphasis on balancing sustainability, cost, and performance in next-generation network systems.

6.1 Self-sustainable energy harvesting

An effective deployment of self-sustainable energy harvesting systems relies on the design of an energy sustainability model that accurately represents the system operation. Similar models can be exploited (i) to properly dimension the energy supply and (ii) to evaluate the system feasibility, trading off sustainability goals, cost objectives (CAPEX and OPEX), and physical and regulatory constraints. To this aim, first, a proper evaluation of the energy demand of the considered system is needed, based on a power model that accurately represents the system energy consumption. Second, to cope with the erratic nature of renewable energy (RE) production, the power model should integrate a reliable representation of the RE production, to capture the dynamics and variability of RE sources. Finally, the energy sustainability model should allow the assessment of multiple performance metrics, focusing both on sustainability targets, and on cost and feasibility constraints. A simple stochastic energy sustainability model is hence proposed based on the power model in [44]. This sustainability model, depicted in Figure 44, aims at yielding a flexible analytical tool that can be effectively adopted for fast evaluation of the system power demand (i.e., low-power sensors, featuring WiFi and 4G/5G interfaces) and RE production (from PV modules adopted to power sensors), without the need for time consuming simulations, with the purpose of properly dimensioning the RE supply, trading off sustainability goals and feasibility constraints. Furthermore, this sustainability model can be easily adapted to different locations, that may feature different profiles of renewable energy production, entailing different levels of average production and variability. As shown in Figure 44, the proposed model takes as inputs the energy demand of the considered system, the RE production, the electricity prices of the energy drawn from the electric grid and the cost for purchasing unitary photovoltaic (PV) panel and battery.

Figure 44. Energy sustainability model.

Based on this model, various performance metrics related to sustainability and cost objectives can be analytically derived. Besides KPIs strictly focused on energy efficiency, the model offers the possibility to integrate additional sustainability KPIs in the evaluation process. In particular, novel KPIs are introduced to measure the utilization of green energy and the level of self-sustainability of the renewable powered system. In addition, the tool can provide measurements of the energy efficiency in terms of renewable energy required to grant a desired performance target, as detailed in the following subsections. Focusing on the defined KPIs (or a subset of them), various sustainability targets or constraints can hence be defined (as reported in Figure 44. Energy sustainability model). Finally, based on the assessment of various KPIs, that are computed as a function of the PV panel capacity and the battery size, the stochastic model allows to identify the feasibility regions for the RE supply (RE generator and energy storage) dimensioning, i.e., the set of PV panel and battery size combinations for which the selected sustainability targets and constraints result respected. A proper dimensioning of the RE supply system can hence be provided, trading off cost and sustainability goals, and the feasibility of the self-sustainable energy harvesting system can effectively be assessed.

6.1.1 Energy sustainability model

A self-sustainable energy harvesting system is considered, consisting of a set of network components (i.e., sensors in UC5) that can be powered by the electric grid and/or by some local renewable energy supply, represented by a PV panel combined with an energy storage unit. Based on [44], an analytical power consumption and production model is derived, that can be flexibly adapted to tailor sustainability goals in various use cases.

6.1.1.1 Renewable energy production model

The amount of RE generated in a day from a PV panel with reference capacity 1 kilowatt-peak [kWp] is modeled with a continuous real-valued random variable, denoted RE_d , as in the stochastic model presented in [44]. RE_d is characterized by a uniform probability distribution, featuring a mean value and a variance which depend on the location. The total daily amount of RE produced during the daylight period, denoted as RE_D , is derived as $RE_D = RE_d \cdot S_{PV}$, where S_{PV} corresponds to the actual PV panel capacity in terms of number of unitary PV panels.

6.1.1.2 Modeling the energy demand and the energy storage

The average daily energy demand, which depends on the considered scenario and application, is reasonably assumed to be constant for our purposes. It is denoted with D , distinguishing between the energy demand during the daytime (i.e., when RE is produced), denoted by D_d , and the energy demand during the night, denoted by D_n . Any extra amount of RE that is not immediately utilized to power the considered system is assumed to be harvested into a storage for future utilization. The capacity of the energy storage, measured in watt-hour [Wh], is denoted with C_B . In addition, the system may also be powered by the electric grid. The average daily amount of energy drawn from the grid is denoted G .

The proposed sustainability model, adapted from [44], is based on the definition of a 3-state Markov chain, depicted in Figure 45, where each state represents a possible battery charge level that is observed in the battery unit at the sunrise. This represents the most critical daytime in terms of energy self-sufficiency. Indeed, at this time RE starts being produced after the night period, during which RE is not generated, hence the battery might result depleted due to the need for drawing energy from the storage to power the system during the night hours. The following three states are defined, as shown in Figure 45:

- **State E:** the battery is empty;
- **State L:** maximum battery charge level observed at the beginning of the day, assuming that, at the beginning of the previous night period (i.e. after the last hour of RE generation on the day before), the battery was at full charge and energy was drained for the system operation during the night;
- **State M:** the battery charge is at an intermediate level between States E and State L.

The transitions between two states i and j occur with time steps of 24 hour, with probability p_{ij} . This Markov model allows to derive analytical formulas from the steady state probabilities, to compute a number of metrics and KPIs as a function of the PV panel capacity and the battery size. Based on the derived formulas, this analytical tool hence allows to identify and delineate the feasibility region for proper PV and storage system dimensioning. This feasibility region includes all the possible combinations of PV panel capacity and battery size that allows to target desired sustainability goals, trading off cost and feasibility constraints, and possible QoS requirements.

Figure 45. Sustainability model based on 3-state Markov chain.

6.1.2 Sustainability-related KPIs

In [44], the RE system dimensioning is only based on the constraint on the maximum allowed battery depletion probability, whereas additional KPIs are embedded in this power model to enable a more elaborated assessment of the system feasibility. The integration of these additional KPIs represents a novel contribution, allowing to deploy a sustainable model for proper RE system dimensioning that can effectively be adapted to different scenarios and requirements. In particular, the following KPIs are defined. These KPIs include sustainability KPIs that are defined in D6.2 [45] of WP6. All of them are derived as a function of PV panel capacity and battery size:

- **Grid energy:** average amount of energy drawn from the grid to power the system;
- **Green/grid energy ratio:** ratio of the average locally produced renewable energy to the average energy drawn from the electric grid consumed to power the system;
- **Energy self-sustainability:** average fraction of time during which the system is powered exclusively by renewable energy, without the need to draw energy from the electric grid. It is derived based on the complementary probability of the battery depletion probability, denoted p_D , that is the probability that the battery is depleted at the beginning of the daytime. It is hence defined as $1 - p_D$. In the case of an off-grid system (powered by renewable energy only), this metric provides a measure of the reliability of the RE supply and, consequently, of the level of service continuity that can be guaranteed (for example, a high value of self-sustainability guarantees that off-grid renewable powered sensors remain active for a minimum desired fraction of time);
- **Sustainability improvement energy efficiency – SIEE:** this KPI falls in the category of the Performance Improvement Energy Efficiency (PIEE) KPIs, as defined in D6.2 [45]. In the considered context, assuming a desired target level of energy self-sustainability higher than x , this KPI is defined as the ratio of the increase of self-sustainability with respect to the baseline case (grid-only powering without any RE supply, in which self-sustainability is null) to the amount of produced renewable energy that is required to obtain an increase of self-sustainability from 0 (baseline case) to the desired target level x ;

The proposed sustainability model will be employed in UC5 to evaluate the sustainability of a system in which sensor devices are powered by RE supply combined with some battery units (with possible backup power provided by the electric grid), compared against the case in which sensor devices are solely powered by the electric grid.

6.2 Energy utilization Edge versus Cloud

In the context of the sustainability solutions, ORO, together with IMEC and Nextworks, are developing an E2E orchestration platform that is taking advantage of ORO's 5G Labs private network topology, that implements the Edge-Cloud continuum concept by including both central cloud and Edge facilities, to monitor and act on the energy utilization data coming from the Edge-deployed applications for both UC1 and UC4.

The target integration setup between ORO, IMEC and Nextworks is showcased in Figure 46. Based on this architecture, ORO delivered on creating the necessary virtualized infrastructure for the envisioned PoC and provided IMEC and Nextworks access to the created VMs using specifically provisioned VPN accounts.

Figure 46. ORO-IMEC-NextWorks integration architecture.

In the last couple of months, IMEC and Nextworks deployed their software components on the virtual appliances and performed the first integration validation tests using generic applications (e.g., Nginx). In the following period, the integration will be extended to include the TUIASI video analytics applications for UC1 and UC4, thus allowing for real-world improvements in the running of the TrialsNet project trials. Proper KPIs will be defined and measured in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed solution.

6.3 Energy aware application design

In the intrinsic definition of the Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) framework, the automated orchestration of network and computing resources should be embedded, using AI/ML agents for tasks like resource prediction, QoS prediction, and anomaly detection. By incorporating power consumption into the set of decision-making conditions, the ZSM framework should support energy-aware designs, promoting more sustainable network solutions. The energy-aware design of future applications aims to address gaps in sustainable software engineering by setting sustainability goals. The focus of these applications is to optimize energy consumption while maintaining high performance and reliability. By leveraging AI/ML techniques for energy prediction, anomaly detection, and resource optimization, such applications contribute to the sustainable management of network resources.

Although programmability has been a key paradigm in networks for some time, recent years brought new concepts for network function programming. One of these emerging concepts is a vertical service which is a service function chain that consists of vertical and network applications as shown in Figure 47. While network applications focus on dynamic resource management, vertical applications are specialized software solutions, designed to leverage cellular connectivity to support and optimize vertical day-to-day operations. For instance, in the Automotive sector, cellular connectivity enables real-time communication between autonomous/teleoperated vehicles and advanced vertical services, providing mission-critical updates about the Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs). This is why vertical service consists of network applications and vertical applications where the network ones are communicating with the network and making changes (e.g., requesting more network resources),

and vertical applications are only focused on consuming these allocated resources to deliver vertical logic (e.g., generating updates for VRUs and vehicles). This integration allows the vertical application to adapt to network conditions. In this section, for simplicity, the building blocks of vertical services are referred to as 6G Apps.

The 5G-PPP made a classification of vertical services as depicted in Figure 47 based on their architectural placement and interaction with the 5G/B5G system [46]. As such, vertical services can be: i) fully integrated within the 5G/B5G system (coupled/delegated model), and ii) partially integrated in the 5G/B5G system, which are within the CSP domain (hybrid model) or are placed in interconnected domains of the CSP (aaS model). This results in three categories [47]:

- **As-a-Service (aaS) Model:** Vertical applications running on the infrastructure of the vertical industries (either on physical premises such as warehouses, ports, control, and server rooms or in the cloud) consume the network application by connecting to the 3GPP network. This way, vertical applications can communicate with the network applications through APIs provided by CSPs.
- **Hybrid Model:** Verticals instantiate a part of their vertical application in network (e.g., Edge), while the other part remains in the vertical domain.
- **Coupled/Delegated Model:** The vertical applications are fully operational and managed by the CSP.

Figure 47. Beyond 5G/6G applications framework.

The 6G networks aim to become significantly more energy efficient, by a factor of 100 compared to 5G and spanning from the RAN to the core network layer. To achieve that, energy efficiency and sustainable design will be also crucial for next-generation 6G Apps [48], and key aspects to consider are:

- **Energy Consumption Monitoring and Optimization:** Future 6G Apps should be capable of continuously monitoring their energy usage. By being aware of their energy consumption, these applications can dynamically adjust their operations, optimizing tasks to reduce energy usage without compromising performance. They can also request adaptation of network parameters like transmission power or switching to more energy-efficient routing paths, to help maintain service quality while minimizing energy consumption.
- **Incorporation of Energy Constraints in Application Blueprints:** 6G Apps should integrate energy constraints into their blueprint, i.e., application descriptor definition [5]. This way, verticals can define minimum and maximum energy consumption levels for their services. The orchestrators such as ZSM should be able to process that information while instantiating the energy-aware service, and to be able to feed that type of information to the applications so that they can adjust their logic to minimize the energy consumption.

- **Collaboration with Network Controllers and Orchestrators:** Apart from applications adjusting their logic to minimize the energy consumption, by interacting closely with network controllers and orchestrators, it will become possible to perform real-time adjustments such as dynamically shifting workloads or reallocating resources to reduce energy use, all while maintaining service quality and adhering to vertical-specific energy requirements.

For instance, adhering to the energy-aware design principles listed above, the energy-aware applications in the context of vehicular communications, such as UC4 “Smart Traffic Management”, could possibly optimize energy usage for future autonomous vehicle systems and onboard sensors, extending vehicle battery life and reducing operational costs. A 6G App can predict the optimal radio link parameters based on historical data and environmental factors (e.g., weather conditions, movement of objects) and then instruct the sensors to adapt their radio settings proactively, optimizing energy usage while ensuring good link quality.

The energy-aware functions in TrialsNet are integrated into both ZSM framework and application design. As described in Section 5.1.1, ZSM framework is already taking into account the energy consumption on the Edge Computing environment where applications are running, and as such it is applying optimization techniques that will minimize energy consumption. In the next phase of planned trial activities, UC4 application will be packaged following the principles of Coupled/Delegated model, and as such, it will be tested in the context of energy-aware optimization techniques. The application functions will subscribe to energy consumption events published by the ZSM framework (monitoring data), and identify its own energy consumption to e.g., reduce resolution of video that is being streamed from the road infrastructure, if that will not significantly affect the service performance (energy vs. performance tradeoff, which will be measured as Performance Improvement Energy Efficiency KPI, defined in D6.2 [45]). The KPI measurements on the energy consumption, i.e., Reduced Energy Consumption and Performance Improvement Energy efficiency, as defined in D6.2 [45], will be correlated with the KVis related to environmental sustainability. Reduced energy consumption will be beneficial for distributed and ubiquitous 5G Edge Computing nodes where applications are running, and having energy-aware application logic in combination with ZSM orchestration decisions being made while taking energy consumption into account will impact the overall energy footprint of the system.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable reported on the latest progresses about the design, development and deployment of the platform and network solutions that are supporting the large-scale trial activities in the context of WP3, WP4 and WP5. The document presented an updated figure of the infrastructures in the different trial sites (i.e., the Italian, Spanish, Romanian and Greek clusters), highlighting the main enhancements with respect to what reported in the latest deliverable D2.2 [2]. For what concern the Turin site, this has already hosted the trials of the UC5 “Control Room in Metaverse” and UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse”, validating the functionalities of the platform and network solutions developed during the first two years of the project. In addition, it should be highlighted that, despite the geographical separation of the infrastructures in clusters, the WP2 activities are anyway creating synergies between the different trial sites. Some technologies, innovations (e.g., Zero-Touch Service Management), and use cases (for example UC6) are going to be executed in more than one infrastructure, setting also the baseline for future expansion of the clusters.

The deliverable then highlighted the ongoing work in Open Call projects. In Option 1 sub-projects, the TrialsNet’s sites are further developed by incorporating new features and/or use cases. This enables enhanced service orchestration and the integration of additional network features that leverage the existing infrastructures. For Option 2, sub-projects involve the establishment of entirely new trial sites, enabling the deployment of additional platform and network solutions as well as a variety of new use cases and related applications. Sub-projects are critical to advancing 5G technologies and providing platforms for further innovation, thus to further strength the outcomes of TrialsNet.

The Security Handbook included in this deliverable described the complete security solution used throughout the TrialsNet infrastructure from cloud to Edge and network security. That includes cloud application protection, virtual network function security, and Edge/IoT security. Network security guarantees user plane and control plane isolation and security through various technologies including network slicing. These security methods protect not only the technological property but also the testing environments themselves, which allows for safe and secure testing experiences.

The document also provided insights into the latest developments in TrialsNet’s Vertical and Horizontal innovations, showcasing how these innovations are enhancing use cases and benefiting external experimenters. The integration of these innovations contributes to the project’s flexibility and capacity for scaling with new applications and features. Innovations design is currently at final stage and the use cases’ applications are utilizing them to improve their performances.

Additionally, this deliverable highlighted some of the key issues regarding network sustainability, specifically energy-efficient approaches like Edge Computing and energy-aware application design, which are going to be utilized in future experiments. These solutions are crucial for the success of future experiments and contribute to the long-term viability of the network. Energy-efficiency KPIs have been also identified and will be finalized in collaboration with WP6 to evaluate their effectiveness in meeting the project’s sustainability objectives.

The next and final deliverable D2.4 of WP2 will report on the finalization of the platform and network solution for each trial site, the development of the final release of the technology solutions related to the TrialsNet Horizontal and Vertical innovations, as well as the finalization of the TrialsNet sustainability solutions, whose KPIs will be measured and evaluated in synergy with WP6.

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Annex A - Open Call infrastructures description for Option 2 sub-projects

This Annex A reports a detailed description of the Option 2 private infrastructures provided by the following sub-projects:

- 5G-enabled Secure Surveillance Sys-tem (5GS3)
- AI4RTC: AI applications for Real-time Charging Load Management
- Automated Tele-Operated Sustainable (ATOS) driving
- Beyond 5G Football Stadium
- Connected Rails: Evaluating 5G for Autonomous Tram Operations
- MediVision-5G (eHealth)
- METACLINIC

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TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

5GS3

Platform and Network solutions description

1 Infrastructure description

The network infrastructure is built around a standalone 5G network consists of a central server, a 5G Core (5GC) and a Radio Access Network (RAN). The 5G Core is the backbone of the infrastructure, providing crucial network services such as data routing, authentication, and mobility management. It enables ultra-low latency, high-speed communication, and scalability by utilizing cloud-native architecture. This core is composed of several key components like the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), User Plane Function (UPF), and Session Management Function (SMF), which work together to ensure efficient communication between the server and connected devices (autonomous robotics).

The Radio Access Network (RAN) is responsible for the wireless connection between the server and the autonomous robotics. It consists of 5G base stations, gNodeBs, which communicate directly with the user devices over radio frequencies. These gNodeBs transmit data to and from the devices while maintaining high throughput and ensuring reliable, uninterrupted connectivity, even in high-density environments. The RAN operates on various frequency bands, allowing for optimal performance and coverage in different scenarios, from urban centers to rural areas. With its ability to handle massive device densities and deliver ultra-fast connections, the 5G RAN ensures that the devices connected to the server can seamlessly transmit data, providing a highly responsive network experience.

2 Equipment and devices connectivity aspects

The private 5G architecture will be using Open5GS Core or Magma Core. Both cores are open-source implementations of a 5G core network, adhering to 3GPP standards. They provide a comprehensive framework for developing and deploying 5G networks. The architecture is structured around the fundamental elements of a standalone 5G core network, managing user authentication, session establishment, and traffic routing, while ensuring seamless connectivity between devices and the network. Standardized interfaces as defined by 3GPP specifications ensure interoperability and compatibility across the system.

3 Deployment areas

The 5GS3 system will be deployed at Athens International Airport (AIA), focusing on critical security areas like perimeter fences, runways, parking lots, and indoor crowded areas. Autonomous robots connected to the private 5G/B5G network, managed by the network partner, will monitor these zones for security threats. The private 5G architecture includes the EPC (Evolved Packet Core), Access Gateways, and Network Gateway, ensuring high-speed, low-latency communication for real-time security operations. This deployment serves as a proof of concept for using autonomous robotic systems to enhance airport security.

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AI4RTC

Platform and Network solutions description

1 Infrastructure description

Most charging hardware that is not connected to a reliable wifi or ethernet connection, use 3G/4G technology to connect to the internet which have higher latencies and smaller bandwidth. 4G Technology has latencies from 30 to 70 milliseconds whereas 5G can have lower latencies from 5 to 20 milliseconds, making it a much more suitable and reliable technology for real-time energy monitoring and charging solutions. Moreover, low latency of 5G enables the implementation of a more accurate load balancing system, that can balance in real-time and with precision the energy supply and demand between the Electric Vehicle chargers and the other energy sources and loads, so that there are no disruptions in the power distribution of a building, campus or a micro-grid, even during peak times

To integrate the new Real Time EV Charging Load management use case to TrialNet we will connect 5 charging stations of the EV Loader network to the commercial 5G SA network of COSMOTE.. Charging stations of the network will be fitted with external 5G routers as they currently do not support 5G Mobile Data connectivity. The 5G computers will be configured and installed near the charging stations by start-up Parity Platform and enable 5G connectivity to the hardware. Charging Stations will be connected to 5G SA network of COSMOTE.

The charging stations will send energy measurements (consumption, power, voltage, temperature, State-of-Charge etc.) in real-time (second/subsecond intervals) to a cloud server. These measurements will then be analyzed in the server and presented in real-time dashboards, to monitor, extract useful insights and use AI to predict the energy consumption, charging patterns and faults.

Security:

IoT sims used are securely configured through VPN to only accept connections from authorized users and networks and to prevent traffic hijacking by malicious actors seeking to obtain PII data of users charging in the stations

2 Equipment and devices connectivity aspects

Hardware used:

External 5G Router (Teltonika RUT241 or ZTE MC801A)

Abb Terra Charging Stations

Low Latency Network Switch (for cases where a single router serves multiple chargers)

Connection

5G routers are installed in the location of the charging stations. They are connected to one or multiple charging stations via ethernet cable. In case 5G routers ports are not sufficient for the number of charger a low latency switch is used.

3 Deployment areas

	Location	# of EV Charging Plugs	Router
L1	4 Seasons Astyr Hotel Vouliagmeni	2 x ABB Terra 22kW	ZTE MC801A
L2	Frontzou Politeia Ioannina	1 x MC Chargers 22kW, 1 payment terminal	Tel RUT241
L3	Office Building in Marousi	12 x Alfen 22 kW	2x Tel RUT241
L4	Ayvens Glyfada Office	Vestel 2x11kW dual charger	Tel RUT241
L5	Municipality of Athens, Serafeio Complex	Ensto Chago 2x11Kw	Tel RUT241

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ATOS driving

Platform and Network solutions description

1 Infrastructure description

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the experimental infrastructure that will be used in our trials, provided by the FNS 6G national testbed (<https://futurenetworkservices.nl/en/>) at the DoIoT Fieldlab (<https://doiot-fieldlab.tudelftcampus.nl>) located in Unmanned Valley (<https://unmannedvalley.nl/>) in the Netherlands, of which TNO is a partner and provides the core network. The test infrastructure includes one Ericsson gNodeB with outdoor antennas giving a coverage of around 500m x 100m of testable road area. At the premise test area, V-Tron’s tele-operated vehicle will connect directly to the 5G SA network via a 5G router. The tele-operation remote station will also be deployed at the test location in an indoor control room where a PC connected to a steering wheel and pedals are installed. At the edge infrastructure, the TNO B5G core with exposed APIs is deployed. Finally, Roboauto’s gateway fleet management component and IMEC’s zero-touch management orchestrator are deployed in their own servers. Each of these components are further described below.

Figure 1 – Architecture of the experimental infrastructure

TNO B5G core: the experimental TNO B5G core will be deployed at the edge infrastructure and will expose the following APIs: (1) Quality-on-demand (QoD) enabling on-demand adaptation of QoS profiles for a particular device (i.e., UE), (2) performance metrics providing subscribers with periodic performance data for a device, and (3) energy consumption giving subscribers the current energy metrics related to 5G core processes.

V-Tron tele-operated vehicle equipped with additional cameras, on-board unit and 5G router. This vehicle will be running the tele-operation software client that will connect to Roboauto’s tele-operation service and be remotely operated by a person located at the vehicle control room. The 5G router will be connected to the TNO B5G core with a private TNO provided SIM card.

Roboauto tele-operation service: the tele-operation service has two main components: (1) tele-operation remote station receiving camera, positioning data from the test vehicles and sending control commands back based on the remote operator at the vehicle control centre; and (2) gateway fleet management used to register vehicle and facilitate the establishment of direct connections between vehicles and tele-operation remote stations. The remote station will consume performance metrics and Quality-on-Demand (QoD) APIs during the trials.

IMEC orchestrator: the energy consumption API will support the orchestration decision making process with sustainability goals when, e.g., performing migration of services between edge nodes. Based on energy

consumption insights, the QoD API will be used to adapt the QoS profile of specific devices in order to control the overall the energy consumption of the network, e.g., by limiting the bandwidth used by certain devices.

Table 1 shows the technical details of the network infrastructure.

Table 1 – Technical description of the network infrastructure

Unmanned Valley: Test driving area		
Coverage area(s)	500m x 100m of road stretch area	
Sectors	4G: 1, 5G: 1	
gNodeB technologies	5G SA, 5G NSA, 4G, NB-IOT, CAT-M – 3GPP release 16	
Frequencies	3,8 GHz (n77), 1.800 MHz (B3), 700 MHz (B28) (test licenses up to 2025)	
Radio	5G massive MIMO, 4G 2x2 MIMO	5G 4x4 MIMO, 4G 2x2 MIMO
B5G core	TNO B5G core - 3GPP release 17	
Server capacity available	Local edge: 228 pCPU, 1,5 TB RAM, 24 TB NVMe SSD-Storage	

2 Equipment and devices connectivity aspects

Table 2 gives a description of the connectivity network interfaces used by the different equipment and devices.

Table 2 – Description of equipment and devices connectivity

Device	Network interface	Description
Tele-operated vehicle (V-Tron)	Direct connection via <u>5G SA connection</u> to the base station in the test location.	Vehicle (Toyota CH-R hybrid) with Drive-by-wire and steer-by-wire functionalities equipped with cameras, 5G router (Sierra wireless), and On-Board Unit (OBU) as processing unit. The router supports both SA and NSA bands with peak downlink of 4.14 Gbps and peak uplink of 660 Mbps.
Tele-operation remote station (Roboauto)	On-premise <u>Ethernet cable connection</u>	The tele-operation remote station equipment consisting of a PC, steering wheel, pedals for remote manoeuvring is connected directly to the test location network via Ethernet cable or wifi
Roboauto/IMEC servers	<u>Internet connection</u>	Roboauto and IMEC servers consume the TNO B5G via exposed OpenAPI with security access keys such as OAuth 2.0 client credentials

3 Deployment areas

Figure 2 shows the area covered by the infrastructure and trial location: ‘Unmanned Valley’, near Leiden, The Netherlands. It consists of a road strip of 500 x 500 meters, which is suitable in terms of length and realistic road traffic environment for testing teleoperation.

Figure 2 – Test site location with highlighted test driving area

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Beyond 5G Football Stadium Platform and Network solutions description

1 Infrastructure description

The Infrastructure of the B5G Football Stadium trial is an end-to-end 5G network installed on a Premier League football stadium installed in the city of Petach-Tikwa in Israel

In the Stadium currently deployed is a 5G Stand-Alone (SA) and Non-Stand-Alone (NSA) Private Network at 3.6 GHz band connected also to the Public Network Core of a Tier-1 operator (Cellcom).

The facility comprises of a medium size football stadium in Israel (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HaMoshava_Stadium) which includes two tribunes (East and West) that together support 11000 spectators in a regular Israeli premier league football game and up to 18,000 spectators in concerts events.

RunEL has completed the deployment and commercialization of a novel 5G Stand Alone (SA) and Non-Stand Alone (NSA) Private/Public network in the stadium, its architecture is depicted in the block diagram to the right.

The 5G network includes 6 cells (3 to cover the East tribune and another 3 to cover the West tribune) installed on the stadium roof and pointing with their directional beam antennas towards the tribunes. Each cell

includes two Radios (4G and 5G) to provide 5G SA and NSA services (as well as 4G) at n78 band (5G) and b7 band (4G). The 3 x West tribune cells are connected by fiber to a Server that runs the DU and the CU modules, the 3 x East tribune cells are connected to another Server which includes DU and CU modules. Both Servers are linked via a Mobile Edge Router (MER) to an on-site local 5G Core to create a 5G SA private network and to an Israeli Tier 1 MNO (Cellcom) public cellular network 4G/5G NSA Core from NOKIA (for users Registration and Billing purposes).

The local 5G private network also includes a Management and Monitoring Module that collects, stores, and analyses the real time data from the network infrastructure and connected users.

Each of the six includes AW2S 5G and 4G Radio Units (RU) connected to two Dell servers running Amarisoft DU and CU SW packages.

The 5G and 4G Radios Units are using RunEL directional antennas specially developed for the Stadium. The DU/CU Servers are connected to a Local Server that runs the Private 5G Core from Druid as well as the Management and Monitoring module and the Stadium special applications server. The local network is also connected via a Firewall to the biggest Tier-1 Public Cellular Operator in Israel (Cellcom) NSA Core Network (from NOKIA).

The 5G Network deployed in the Stadium is already commercially operated using the 5G and 4G Spectrum license owned by the MNO (Cellcom) including the required approved licenses and permits from various Israel authorities including the Ministry of Communication, Environmental Affairs Ministry, Defense Ministry, Israel Cyber Authority as well as the MNO approval for connection with his public network.

The PT Stadium 5G Network main features are:

1. Frequency Bands: n78 (5G) and b7 (4G)
2. Bandwidth: 100MHz (5G) and 20 MHz (4G)
3. Total 5G Capacity: 6Gbps (DL) 0.5 Gbps (UL)
4. Max User Terminal Experience 1 Gbps (DL) 100 Mbps (UL) 25 Mbps
5. Max number of simultaneous connected UE's: 18,000
6. Duplexing Mode: TDD (76.5% downlink, 23.5% uplink, cycle of 2.5msec.)

The Stadium 5G Network supports many 5G UE terminals from various suppliers (Apple, Samsung, One Plus, Huawei, etc.) that have been tested and approved by the Tier 1 Operator.

2 Equipment and devices connectivity aspects

The connection between the UEs and the RU is over the air at 3.6 GHz (5G) or 2.7 GHz (4G). The communication between the RUs and the DU is CIPRI over Fiber. The communication between the DU and CU is internal and proprietary of Amarisoft. The connection between the CU and the Druid 5G SA private core or the Nokia NSA public core is based on 3GPP N2, N# standard interface

3 Deployment areas

The infrastructure described herein installed in the football stadium covers mainly the East and West tribunes of the Stadium and the Football Field with Line of Site connectivity since the RUs' antennas are installed on the Stadium Roof on both sides of the stadium as shown in the picture below:

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Connected Rails

Platform and Network solutions description

1 Infrastructure description

Infrastructure in Florence

The 5G network infrastructure for Connected Rails in Florence is built on Vodafone's commercial network. Specifically, this network uses a non-standalone (NSA) deployment, where the 5G network operates alongside the existing 4G LTE infrastructure. In this setup, 5G primarily handles high-speed data transfer, while control signaling and core functions still depend on the 4G network. As a result, many advanced services typically associated with 5G, such as ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), network slicing, and positioning services cannot be fully realized in this configuration.

Connected Rails network infrastructure includes small Ethernet networks on the edge linked by a commercial 5G network. Furthermore, the signals from all the g-NBs available in the area where the Tram 1013 is in service (usually line T1 of the Florence tramway) are used to collect relevant measurements. Data are stored in a storage system onboard of the tram vehicle and postprocessed in the relevant server on ground.

A commercial 5G link provided by a local MNO (Mobile Network Operator) is also used to connect onboard systems to cloud OCC (Operation Control Center) in GTSI premises and to create traffic load to test link performances along the line. A Vodafone SIM is used.

Ethernet networks are:

1. Onboard tram network which links the NGAP system (whose aim is estimating accurately the tram position using only onboard sensors, such as RADAR, IMU and GNSS) to the 5G positioning system based on an SDR board.
2. OCC network in the GTSI premises where data collected onboard can be postprocessed and displayed.

Data involved in the process cannot be considered sensitive and no security mechanism was necessary and therefore applied.

Figure 1-1: Florence Infrastructure description

Sandbox environment in UPC labs

This environment is being deployed in the laboratory premises of UPC. The sandbox implementation is shown in Figure 1-2. The hardware for the sandbox consists of a host, which contains a Virtual Machine (VM) that represents the onboard equipment of the tram. In the VM, Docker and Minikube, which is a lightweight version of Kubernetes, are installed. The role of Docker is to enable the creation and running of containers. Minikube allows the management and automation of the deployment, scaling, and operating of containers in the environment. Minikube will enable to test the different strategies for managing critical and non-critical applications by using different policies. Relying on Docker and Minikube, critical and non-critical applications are deployed as containers. To be managed by Kubernetes, the containers are deployed in pods, each one with a container in the namespace “sandbox-app”. These two containers emulate the requirement of computer resources of the critical and non-critical applications in the onboard equipment on the tram. This emulation is controlled by Script #1

and Script #2 that configure the load of computational resources required by the critical application (e.g., the NGAP or ODT applications) and the non-critical application (i.e., video server), respectively. To monitor the computational resources usage by these applications, Prometheus and Grafana applications are deployed in different pods in the namespace “monitoring”. These tools will be used to assess the impact of the different Kubernetes/Minikube policies and different computational resources requirements on computing resource usage for each application. As described in the Connected Rails proposal document, this network architecture will be then deployed in the GTSI laboratory in Florence, wherein NGAP and ODT systems will be installed in the containers.

Figure 1-2: Sandbox environment in UPC premises.

This network architecture will be then deployed in the GTSI laboratory in Florence, wherein NGAP and ODT systems will be installed in the containers.

2 Equipment and devices connectivity aspects

2.1 Florence equipment

The Florence equipment involved in the trial can be included in two groups:

1. Onboard systems
2. Ground systems

2.1.1 Onboard systems

Onboard systems are installed on tram 1013.

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1. Sensors: RADAR, IMU, GNSS | 3. Router/Switch: Teltonika Rutx50 |
| 2. OD and NGAP processing unit: Syslogic RML A3 | 4. SDR board: USRP E312 by Ettus Research |
| | 5. 5G Antenna: TOP_120_AMR |

2.1.2 Ground systems

Servers managing the cloud applications are hosted in the OCC are ordinary server and display system which is useless to define in details. They are:

1. Server to monitor the tram position along the line and display it on screens.
2. Server to postprocess the measurements of 5G signal collected by SDR board to estimate the tram position

2.2 Sandbox equipment

A virtual machine (VM) has been created in one of the servers available at UPC with the minimal requirements of this platform. Specifically, the created VM has the following features:

- | | |
|---------------------------|-------------------------|
| 1. CPU: 4 | b. API version: 1.43 |
| 2. RAM: 6 Giga | c. OS/Arch: linux/amd64 |
| 3. OS: Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS | d. Context: default |
| 4. Docker installed: | 5. Minikube installed. |
| a. Version: 24.0.7 | a. Version: v1.33.1 |

3 Deployment areas

The infrastructure involved in the trial is the commercial 5G infrastructure that several providers (TELECOM, WIND, VODAFONE...) are operating in the urban area of Florence, particularly in the sections in the surroundings of tramway line 1 (T1).

As far as the technical aspects are concerned, the system could work also on the other tramway line (T2) if GEST (tramway system management company) can operate vehicle 1013 along T2.

Figure 3-1 Line T1 and T2 of Florence Tramway system.

TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

MediVision5G

Platform and Network solutions description

1 Infrastructure description

The network infrastructure that is going to be deployed for this project consists of a “in-a-box” solution, 5G SA, powered by the physical elements shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: physical elements composing the deployment

- **RRU:** The remote radio unit selected for this project is the Askey SCE2120 ([link](#)). It is a all-in-one RRU+SBC to host CU/DU or vRAN. This feature makes the solution extremely compact; ideal for a versatile and transportable design. The SCE2120 supports N48, N77, and N78 bands, up to 100MHz bandwidth and 2x2 MIMO with maximum transmission power of 24dBm. It integrates a 65° patch antenna.
- **CU+DU:** To operate the RAN, we opted for Node-H CU/DU integrated software solution ([link](#)). Node-H is a German vRAN and O-RAN software vendor specialized in small- and femto- cells. The main reason that drove the decision to select this vendor, is the amount of metrics and KPIs exposed by its RAN segment (more than 90). The CU/DU is an integrated ORAN system, offering certain flexibility in comparison to a monolithic vRAN such as the exposure of the O1 interface. The vendor is also considering future releases in which other interfaces such as the E2 might be exposed.
- **Core Network Server:** this server is dedicated to host the Core Network. Someone might argue that the same server could host both the core network and the application in virtualized environment. It is actually possible, and current deployment in the lab has this configuration. However, having the Core Network running in bare-metal proved to be more stable and much easier to troubleshoot; which is preferred for the final deployment. The server selected is a general-purpose COTS server from Supermicro, belonging to the SIS12D2 server family. The peculiarity of this server family is that it's short-depth 1U server, which means that its depth is the half of a normal rack server. This allow the in-a-box solution to be much more compact.
- **Core Network:** The Core Network selected for this project is Open5Gs ([link](#)). It is a 5GC+EPC open-source implementation, to which Neutron contributed, developing some APIs for automation and the NEF component. An open-source Core Network is ideal to reduce the CapEx of the PoC. In case the project will reach a commercialization phase with the hospitals, there is a preliminary agreement in progress with Druid Software to deploy the Raemis 5GC (R16) carrier grade Core network ([link](#)).
- **Edge server:** As per the hardware hosting the Core Network, also the applications are hosted on a Supermicro SIS12D2 family server. In this case the characteristics of the server are sufficient to host the OS, agents, virtual environment, VIM, and of course the application. The server features an Intel Xeon Gold 6530 (32C/64T) processor, 64GB DDR-5 RAM, 2x Gen5 PCI-e socket, 1TB SSD, 4x 1Gbps RJ45 adapter card.
- **Switch:** the switch is a programmable Cisco Catalyst switch. Its function is mere transport network, but with traffic segregation capacity. This allows to separate the traffic and create end-to-end slices to ensure the higher QoS possible.

- Gateway router: the gateway Router is a COTS router with NAT and firewall capabilities. It is used just to separate the private 5G SA network from any other networks or IP infrastructures. The private 5G SA network has its own DHCP service running, assigning the IP to the applications and UEs connected following specific CIDR domains and masking rules depending on the slicing necessities. The NAT is a necessary component to connect the private 5G SA network to other networks avoiding IP conflicts or DHCP duplicating messages. An enterprise grade router from Mikrotik or Ubiquity are suitable for the purpose.
- CPE: The CPE has a double role: (i) adapt the connectivity interface for the UE - i.e. 5G to Wi-Fi, (ii) work as a watchdog and UX monitoring device. Some of the UEs available to the medical team might not be equipped with 5G connectivity, but Wi-Fi might be the option. An industrial-grade CPE as the Teltonika RUTX50 ([link](#)), Nexcom DTA1164W ([link](#)), Milesight UR75 ([link](#)), or Cradlepoint E3000 ([link](#)) might serve the purpose. Some models like the Nexcom DTA1164W have been recently tested with a set of dockerized tools to perform connectivity and performance tests.
- Wi-Fi AP: for Countries/locations where 5G spectrum is not available, the RRU will be substituted by a Wi-Fi Access Point. To have a higher degree of control over the Wi-Fi, we selected an OpenWiFi ([link](#)) compliant system, so that it will be possible to gather more information and metrics from it. The model selected is the Edgecore EAP102 ([link](#)) for its compact form-factor in relation to the very high-end performance. The Wi-Fi 6, 4x4:4 MU-MIMO allows segregate traffic among 4 UL/DL streams, kind of segregating traffic to emulate what we should get with a 5G slice. It won't be the same, but it seems to be the best approximation available allowing to maintain the same UX flow for the user.
- UE: The principal UE for this application is the AR headset. The market offers different options, from the Microsoft HoloLens, Realware HMT and Navigator series, Epson Moverio series, Rokid Glass series, Vuzix M series, etc. The surgeon will choose the most comfortable headset. According to the tests performed so far, the vast majority of the surgeons preferred the Realware HMT1 and Navigator 500.
- Cloud instance: An AWS cloud instance will be used to collect the metrics and monitoring the network. The management and orchestration platform will keep track of the changes in the configuration too.
- Secured MQTT communication: the communication between the local agent (in the edge server) and the cloud instance will happen using MQTT in a secure IoTCore tunnel. Despite the communication with the cloud instance, no data will leave the premise. The cloud instance only take care of the control and management planes.

2 Equipment and devices connectivity aspects

Three different ways of connecting the UE have been considered:

- UE to 5G RRU. For those UEs that supports 5G SA connectivity embedding a 5G module, this will be the preferred option.
- UE to CPE (via Wi-Fi, Ethernet, or USB), CPE to RRU. This approach can work for those UEs that don't support direct 5G SA connectivity. Depending if the device is mobile or not, it can be connected to the CPE via Wi-Fi, ethernet, or USB. Being the AR headset the principal UE, it will use Wi-Fi since the mobility is in general a stringent requirement. However other type of devices might be connected using ethernet or USB. The CPE acts as an intermediary between the 5G interface and the other communication interfaces. An industrial CPE doesn't add a substantial latency to the communication. From the preliminary measures in the lab, it has not been possible to measure precisely the latency introduced by the CPE, which lets believe that the latency added is below the millisecond.
- UE to the Wi-Fi AP. This type of connectivity will be used in those cases where 5G spectrum is not available.

In general, all the UEs considered for the project are 2x2 MIMO, both for 5G than for Wi-Fi. Some supports already Wi-Fi 6, but the majority is Wi-Fi 5 compliant. The RAN has been dimensioned considering these requirements.

3 Deployment areas

The principal area of deployment is the surgery theatre. The average surgery room ranges from 35 to 60 square meters, while the required coverage area is very limited and can be approximated to 16 - 25 square meters. In fact, the surgeon and the surgical team do not roam around the room, but rather tend to occupy the area around the surgery bed.

In terms of interference, external interference are often negligible. Surgery rooms are generally well protected and often at the ground or underground floors. External signals (cellular and Wi-Fi) struggle to penetrate the location. Self-induced interference might be problematic. The area is rich of metal and reflective materials. Medical devices are EM-shielded with Faraday cages that might cause uncontrolled reflections phenomena. Nevertheless, illuminating the area from the top (ie using the false ceiling) consistently reduces such phenomena.

A single RRU/AP per surgery theatre is considered more than enough to provide good quality signal strength all over the area of coverage. The transmission power will be regulated to reduce reflection issues.

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METACLINIC

Platform and Network solutions description

1 Infrastructure description

Figure 1 - High-level architecture of the METACLINIC platform

The METACLINIC project will rely on both commercial and ad-hoc network infrastructure provided by Turkcell to facilitate the trial. Turkcell will offer its 5G Standalone (SA) core network, which supports both mmWave and sub-6 GHz frequencies, enabling high-speed, low-latency communication essential for the VR-based healthcare applications used in the project. In Use Case 1, focused on emergency medical interventions, the project will utilize mmWave technology for ultra-fast data transmission. Meanwhile, sub-6 GHz frequency will be employed in Use Case 2, which involves remote treatments across different locations, providing broader coverage. To guarantee the necessary performance for these applications, the network will incorporate network slicing, creating a dedicated virtual network slice optimized specifically for healthcare needs, ensuring the required bandwidth, low latency, and high communication reliability.

For ad-hoc, private, and experimental deployments, Ericsson AIR5322 active antenna supporting mmWave frequency with n258 band, and Baseband6648 will be used. And, 8x100MHz bandwidth will be used at n258 band with this configuration. The setup includes the installation of General Mobile Customer Premises Equipment (CPE), which will connect to Turkcell’s 5G mmWave network, enabling seamless and high-speed communication in areas where clinicians are not physically present. If the environment is suitable during the time of the demonstration, the demonstration will be held in Kınalada, İstanbul. Additionally, this setup will allow the project to test innovative solutions, ensuring that the necessary infrastructure is in place to support healthcare applications requiring high bandwidth and low latency. The project also incorporates robust communication security measures, including VPNs and tunnels, to safeguard sensitive medical data. The core infrastructure will leverage Turkcell’s existing cloud services and core network located in Kartal, İstanbul.

The software platform will consist of several key components, including a multiplayer server, media server, content server, backend APIs, and VR clients. We will deploy all components as Docker containers on a dedicated server computer connected to the 5G core network. The multiplayer server, responsible for real-time synchronization between users, the media server for streaming audio and video, and the content server delivering VR assets will all run as containers, ensuring isolation, ease of deployment, and scalability. The backend APIs handling authentication, account management, and core business logic will also be containerized and deployed on the same server. VR clients, running on users’ local devices, will connect to these containerized services over the 5G network, benefiting from low latency and high bandwidth. This setup enables a tightly integrated environment with the 5G infrastructure, providing enhanced performance and responsiveness for users, while Docker ensures modularity and easier management of the platform components.

2 Equipment and devices connectivity aspects

The METACLINIC trial will utilize several key devices and equipment, all connected to the 5G network through a combination of direct connections and CPE. The primary devices include Meta Quest 3 VR headsets used by clinicians and patients for immersive medical consultations. These VR headsets, which do not have direct cellular network capabilities, will be connected via routers to the 5G network. In Use Case 1, CPEs will be deployed in Kınalıada (if the conditions will be feasible, otherwise demonstrations will be held in Küçükyalı) to establish a connection to Turkcell's 5G mmWave network, ensuring high-speed and low-latency communication. For Use Case 2, the devices located at multiple sites will connect through Turkcell's 5G SA core network using standard 5G modems operating in the sub-6 GHz band. This setup ensures reliable, secure, and high-performance connectivity for the VR-based healthcare applications during the trial.

3 Deployment areas

The METACLINIC trial infrastructure will cover multiple locations to simulate diverse healthcare scenarios. The primary trial locations are within Türkiye, including Turkcell's Küçükyalı Plaza in Istanbul, which will serve as the central hub for clinicians, and Kınalıada, one of the Prince Island, where a mobile 5G infrastructure will be temporarily installed to support the 5G mmWave network used in Use Case 1. In Use Case 2, the trial will extend to multiple cities, specifically Izmir and Ankara, where patients will be connected remotely to clinicians located in Istanbul. Turkcell's 5G SA network, along with sub-6 GHz and mmWave frequency bands, will ensure seamless connectivity across these geographically distributed locations, enabling high-performance VR interactions for remote medical consultations.